

METHODIST THEOLOGICAL SCHOOL

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON AUGUSTINE'S AND WESLEY'S CONCEPTS OF
PREVENIENT GRACE

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TING MOI KIENG

SIBU

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ABSTRACT

This thesis is an explorative study to compare Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace, in order to find out their similarities and differences. The study reveals 16 similarities and 11 differences between Augustine's and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace. From these findings, this thesis further infers that some kinds of relationships exist between Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace. Since the similarities outnumber the differences and relationships possibly exist between Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace, this thesis further suggests that instead of labelling Wesley's concept of prevenient grace as semi-Pelagian, it is perhaps justifiable to call it semi-Augustinian. Finally, this study invites readers to further examine the suggested possible relationships between Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace, to study relationships between their other theological concepts, and even to construct an Augustinian-Wesley legacy.

USAGE OF TERMS

A few terms need to be clarified. First, the term ‘prevenient’ cannot be found in the English dictionary but is a term used in theology to mean ‘before’. Its precise meaning is explained in this thesis. The term ‘prevenience’ is noun for the adjective ‘prevenient.’

Second, in this thesis, the term ‘gratuitous’ is not a derogatory term as in the contemporary usage, but is a commendatory term used in English translation of Augustine’s works to describe the free grace of God. The term ‘gratuity’ is noun for the adjective ‘gratuitous.’

Third, the term ‘man’ is a term that includes both male and female. Its singular form is used not to refer a particular person, but a person that represents a group of people with the same experience.

Fourth, the term ‘divine’ has the same meaning as ‘God’s’ and their usage is interchangeable.

Fifth, ‘Augustin’ is alternative spelling for ‘Augustine.’ In this thesis, the author will use ‘Augustine’ instead of ‘Augustin.’ However, for the titles of his works in footnotes and bibliography, the author will follow the original spelling.

When a quoted term is used for the first time, it is used with quotation marks and is footnoted. But its subsequent usage is usually not bracketed with quotation marks and not footnoted, and should be understood that it has the same meaning and is quoted from the same source as the first usage. Some of the examples of the quoted terms are saving grace, convincing grace, justifying grace, sanctifying grace, free for all, free in all, natural man, natural conscience and natural state.

INTRODUCTION

In the history of Christianity, Augustine and Wesley are two prominent figures in two different centuries. Augustine was a Church father who lived from fourth to fifth century (AD354 – AD430), but his influence goes beyond his centuries. Until today, Augustine's influence can still be seen in Christianity. For example, people of the Reformed tradition claim that they inherit the Augustinian legacy.

Similarly, Wesley also influenced Christianity in his century and centuries after him. Today, Wesley's influence can also be seen in Christianity. For example, the church that Wesley began (Methodist) continues to exist and grow.

Is there any relationship between these two prominent figures? Almost all scholars agree that Calvin was greatly indebted to Augustine in doing his theology. Sometimes we may even think that Calvin had interpreted Augustine very accurately, and those who were against Calvin's theology and Calvinism were also against Augustine. Since Wesley was strongly against Calvin's and Calvinistic doctrine of predestination, then we must come to conclusion that there is no relationship between Augustine and Wesley. Is it true that there is no relationship between Augustine and Wesley?

Concerning the relationship between Augustine and Wesley, Thomas J. Oord has a different opinion. In his article "Types of Wesleyan Philosophy: The General Landscape and My Own Research Agenda", he claims that "among the philosophers Wesley is known to have read are notables such as Aristotle, Augustine...."¹ In other words, Wesley was influenced by Augustine to some extent in doing his own theology. In response to Oord's claim, this thesis aims to explore the relationship between Augustine and Wesley in the aspect of prevenient grace. Thus, this thesis aims to compare Augustine's and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace, in order to answer a few questions. First, what are the similarities and differences

¹ Thomas J. Oord, "Types of Wesleyan Philosophy: The General Landscape and My Own Research Agenda," *Wesleyan Theological Journal* 39, no. 1 (Spring 2004): 155.

between Augustine and Wesley's concepts? Second, what relationships between Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace can be inferred from the similarities and differences between them? Third, what are the implications of the similarities and differences between Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace?

Structure

In studying the relationship between Augustine's and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace, Chapter One of this thesis will first examine how Wesley used the works of Augustine. Then, in Chapter Two the author of this thesis will attempt to review briefly scholars' studies on Augustine's doctrine of grace, and from their studies the author will attempt to develop a framework to study Augustine's concept of prevenient grace. With this framework, the author will attempt to study briefly Augustine's concept of prevenient grace in Chapter Three. Next in Chapters Four and Five, the author will repeat the same process for studying Wesley's concept of prevenient grace. Lastly in Chapter Six, with the findings of the studies on Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace, the author will compare their concepts of prevenient grace in order to mark out their similarities and differences. From these similarities and differences, relationships between Augustine's and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace may be inferred. These relationships will enrich our understandings on Augustine's and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace, our spiritual and evangelistic lives.

Background and Significance

Why does the author choose to compare Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace? First, Augustine was a Latin Church Father in Hippo during the fourth and fifth century. During his life time, he wrote an enormous amount of philosophical, doctrinal or theological, exegetical, apologetic and polemical works.² Although he did not write any book

² *Evangelical Dictionary Theology*, 1987 ed., s.v. "Augustine of Hippo," by Norman L. Geisler.

on systematic theology, his works cover a wide range of Christian theology, including the theology of God, creation, sin, man, Christ and salvation, as well as Christian ethics.³ His theology was recognised as orthodox. He could be considered as the father of orthodox theology, who left with us a legacy, known as Augustinian legacy. Theologians after him, especially those reformists including Martin Luther and John Calvin, used his works as their main resources in constructing their theology. Not only that, his influence in the form of Augustinianism still prevails until today. This gives the author a good reason to study Augustine's theology, particularly in the concept of prevenient grace.

Second, Wesley is the founder of Methodism. He also did not write any book on systematic theology, but left with us a large amount of works, though the amount is smaller than that of Augustine. His works also cover a wide range of Christian theology, as analyzed by Randy L. Maddox in his book *Responsible Grace*. As Methodists, it is our responsibility and privilege to study critically and reconstruct Wesley's theology, and to inherit the heritage Wesley left with us.

Third, as mentioned above, Oord claims that "among the philosophers Wesley is known to have read are notables such as Aristotle, Augustine..."⁴ From the indexes of the series of *The Works of John Wesley* published by Abingdon Press, it is notable that Wesley cited Augustine's works in his works. Thus, it is obvious that to some extent Augustine is believed to have influenced Wesley, either positively or negatively. These provide us with valid reasons to compare Wesley and Augustine, to see if any relationship exists between them.

We have seen a few crucial reasons the author chooses to compare Augustine and Wesley. But why does the author compare their concepts of prevenient grace? Augustine is

³ *Evangelical Dictionary Theology*, "Augustine of Hippo."

⁴ Oord, "Types of Wesleyan Philosophy," 155.

called “the great preacher of grace.”⁵ The doctrine of grace is the centre of Augustine’s theology,⁶ and “prevenient” grace is one of the important themes in his doctrine of grace.⁷ Interestingly, prevenient grace is also one of the important themes in Wesley’s doctrine of grace. Wesley’s prevenient grace is one of most controversial themes in his theology, where some Calvinists would condemn as semi-pelagian.⁸

By comparing Wesley’s concept of prevenient grace with Augustine’s, it is hoped that the similarities and differences between them could be identified; and from these similarities and differences, relationships between them could be inferred, and Augustine’s influence on Wesley’s concept of prevenient grace, if any, may be traced out. We know that Augustine opposed Pelagius, Pelagianism and semi-Pelagianism.⁹ If Wesley’s concept of prevenient grace is proved to be influenced by Augustine, then the comment made by those Calvinists who condemn Wesley as semi-pelagian may be refuted.

To conclude, this comparative study on Augustine and Wesley’s concepts of prevenient grace is significant enough to be carried out.

⁵ Benjamin B. Warfield, “Introductory Essay on Augustin and the Pelagian Controversy,” in *NPNF1-05. St. Augustin: Anti-Pelagian Writings*, ed. Philip Schaff [book on-line] (Grand Rapids: Christian Classics Ethereal Library, 2004, accessed 2 January 2005); available from <http://www.ccel.org/ccel/schaff/npnf105.html>; Internet; p.70. *NPNF1-05* is electronic version for *A Select Library of the Nicene and Post-Nicene Fathers of the Christian Church*, vol. v, *St. Augustin: Anti-Pelagian Writings*, ed. Philip Schaff (Edinburgh: T & T Clark; Grand Rapids: W.M. B. Eerdmans, 1887).

⁶ *Ibid.*; *Augustine through the Age: An Encyclopedia*, 1999 ed., s. v. “Grace,” by J. Patout Burns.

⁷ Warfield, “Introductory Essay on Augustin and the Pelagian Controversy,” 70.

⁸ A debate is going on to argue if Wesley’s soteriology is semi-Pelagian. Some scholars such as William Maclean and Dan S claim that Wesley’s soteriology is semi-Pelagian, whereas some scholars such as Victor A. Shepherd and Reformed theologian Archibald Alexander Hodge claim that Wesley’s soteriology is not semi-Pelagian. See William Maclean, *Arminianism – Another Gospel* [article on-line] (N.p.: N.p., 1965, accessed 8 October 2005); available from www.tracts.ukgo.com/arminianism.doc; Internet; Dan S, *Church History: The Unholy Alliance of Nearly 2,000 Years* [article on-line] (N.p.: WithChrist.org, 1996-2005, accessed 8 October 2005); available from <http://withchrist.org/unholy.htm>; Internet; Archibald Alexander Hodge, *Outlines of Theology: Pelagianism, Semi-Pelagianism & Augustinianism* [article on-line] (N.p.: The Church on the Threshold, n.d., accessed 8 October 2005); available from <http://www.monergism.com/thethreshold/articles/onsite/semi-pelagian.html>; Internet; Victor A. Shepherd, “John Wesley: A Parent to be Honoured,” *The United Church Observer* (September 1984) [article on-line]; available from <http://www.victorshepherd.on.ca/Wesley/newpage25.htm>; Internet; accessed 8 October 2005; *Wikipedia*, 2005 ed., s. v. “Talk: Prevenient Grace” [encyclopaedia on-line] (St. Petersburg: Wikimeida foundation, 2005, accessed 7 October 2005); available from http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Talk:Prevenient_grace; Internet.

⁹ Warfield, “Introductory Essay on Augustin and the Pelagian Controversy,” 70.

Methods

The method that the author employs is library research. Two types of works will be studied for both Augustine's and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace. The first type of materials is primary sources. Both Augustine and Wesley's works will be examined. However, as it is beyond the author's ability to study all their works, only those portions related to prevenient grace will be analysed.

The second type of materials is scholars' works. Works of scholars on Augustine and Wesley's doctrines of grace will be used. For instance, works of Benjamin B. Warfield and J. Patout Burns on Augustine's doctrine of grace and Albert C. Outler, Kenneth J. Collins and Randy L. Maddox on Wesley's doctrine of grace will be studied.

Warfield and Burns are prominent Reformed scholars. Warfield was a New Testament scholar, a systematic and Reformed theologian, who used to be the Principal of Princeton Theological Seminary and produced a lot of works.¹⁰ Burns, who graduated from Yale University with Doctor of Philosophy (Ph. D) in the history of theology, is presently is an Edward A. Malloy Professor of Catholic Studies in Vanderbilt Divinity School and is "co-editor of the Journal of Early Christian Studies"; he is also a prolific writer.¹¹

Outler, Collins and Maddox are distinguished Wesleyan scholars. Outler graduated from Yale University with a Ph. D degree, and is considered "a 20th century American Methodist theologian and philosopher ... one of the most important Wesley scholars in the history of the Church as well as the first real United Methodist theologian."¹² Collins, who graduated with a Ph. D from Drew University, presently is a professor of historical theology and Wesley Studies and an expertise in "Wesley Studies, American Christianity, History of

¹⁰ Samuel G. Craig, *Benjamin B. Warfield* [article on-line] (N.p.: Grace Online Library, 2005, accessed 7 October 2005); available from <http://www.graceonlinelibrary.org/articles/full.asp?id=38|38|529>; Internet.

¹¹ James Patout Burns, *Curriculum Vitae* [article on-line] (Nashville: Vanderbilt University, 2005, accessed 7 October 2005); available from <http://www.vanderbilt.edu/gradschool/religion/faculty/facultypages/burns.html>; Internet.

¹² *Wikipedia*, 2005 ed., s. v. "Albert Outler" [encyclopaedia on-line] (St. Petersburg: Wikimeida foundation, 2005, accessed 7 October 2005); available from http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Albert_Outler; Internet.

Spirituality, Historical Theology”]; he publishes a lot of books and articles in journals.¹³

Maddox is “the Paul T. Walls Professor of Wesleyan Theology at Seattle Pacific University” and “a recognized authority on both John Wesley's theology and the theological developments in later Methodism, as well as active in scholarship on the nature of evangelicalism.”¹⁴

Studies on these prominent and distinguished Reformed and Wesleyan theologians are probably enough to give us a brief literature review on Augustine and Wesley’s doctrine of grace, in order to develop a framework to study Augustine’s and Wesley’s concepts of prevenient grace.

Scope and Limitation

The scope of this thesis is limited to Augustine’s and Wesley’s concepts of prevenient grace. The methods of this study bring two inevitable limitations to the study. First, since the author of this thesis is not trained in Latin, he can only study the English translations of Augustine’s works. Understandably the use of translations instead of the original language may in some ways affect the accuracy of the study. However, this limitation can be compensated by the use of *A Select Library of the Nicene and Post-Nicene Fathers of the Christian Church*, volumes i to vi. These volumes of works are recognised as the authoritative English translations and standard reference books for the works of the Church fathers.

The second limitation of this thesis is that the study of primary sources is limited to the portions of Augustine’s and Wesley’s works that are related to prevenient grace. The study of Augustine’s works focuses on his anti-Pelagian works, whereas the study of Wesley’s works focuses on his sermons. Although the scope may seem to be narrow, it nevertheless represents the mature thoughts of Augustine and Wesley.

¹³ Asbury Theological Seminary, *Dr. Kenneth J. Collins* [article on-line] (Orlando: Asbury Theological Seminary, 2005, accessed 7 October 2005); available from http://www.ats.wilmore.ky.us/about/faculty/bios/ken_collins.htm; Internet.

¹⁴ Counterbalance Foundation, *Counterbalance Meta Library: Randy Maddox* [article on-line] (Seattle: Counterbalance Foundation, 2005, accessed 7 October 2005); available from <http://www.meta-library.net/bio/randym-body.html>; Internet.

CHAPTER 1

WESLEY AND AUGUSTINE

As identified by some Wesleyan scholars who edited Wesley's works, such as Albert C. Outler,¹⁵ Gerald R. Cragg,¹⁶ Oliver A. Beckerlegge¹⁷ and Rupert E. Davies,¹⁸ Wesley had indeed quoted Augustine's works, used phrases which were also used by Augustine and commented on Augustine. Thus, it is obvious that Wesley had read Augustine's works and other ancient works that Augustine had read. Wesley agreed with or was influenced by Augustine in some theological issues, but in some other concepts he might have disagreed with Augustine. In other words, Wesley read and used Augustine critically.

Based on the editorial works done by Outler, Cragg, Beckerlegge, and Davies on the works of John Wesley, this chapter will attempt to examine in what way Wesley was influenced by Augustine or used the same sources Augustine might have used, and how he commented on Augustine, in the aspects of God's providence, governance and works on believers, as well as aspects of human condition, ethics and comments on Pelagius.

1.1 On God's Providence

First, regarding God's providence, Wesley quoted Augustine's *Confessions*, III.xi: "thou presidest over each creature as if it were the universe, and over the universe as over each individual creature"¹⁹ three times.²⁰

¹⁵ Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1986).

¹⁶ Gerald R. Cragg, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 11, *The Appeals to Men of Reason and Religion and Certain Related Open Letters*, by John Wesley (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1989).

¹⁷ Oliver A. Beckerlegge, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 7, *A Collection of Hymns for the Use of The People Called Methodists*, by John Wesley (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1983).

¹⁸ Rupert E. Davies, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 9, *The Methodist Societies: History, Nature, and Design*, by John Wesley (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1989).

¹⁹ "Ita praesides singulis sicut universes, et universes sicut singulis." (Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley, 57, 372, 372n72, 548, 548n71; Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 3, *Sermons III: 71-114*, by John Wesley [Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1986], 93, 94, 94n23.)

In all three quotations, Wesley agrees totally with Augustine. In his sermon 67 “On Divine Providence”, after explaining the scriptural teachings on divine providence, he claims, “We may then sum up the whole scriptural doctrine of providence in that fine saying of St. Austin, *Ita praesides singulis sicut universes, et universes sicut singulis!*”²¹ From this statement, it is obvious that Wesley accepts Augustine’s words wholly, and believes that these words are not only scriptural but indeed conclude the whole scripture’s teachings on divine providence.

To what extent does divine providence operate? Quoting Augustine’s words “[God] presided over each creature as if it were the universe, and over the universe as over each individual creature” as his support, Wesley identifies the twofold characteristics of divine providence – general and particular. Wesley does not mean two types of divine providence, but two characteristics of divine providence, which attribute to the extensiveness of divine providence, and these two characteristics, indeed, are of the same nature, as God presided “over the whole universe as over every single person, over every single person as over the whole universe.”²² Wesley further explains that divine providence “must extend to all persons and all things,”²³ no matter how great or how little the things are, for “nothing is small in [God’s] sight that in any degree affects the welfare of any that fear God and work righteousness.”²⁴ Thus, everything “except only our own sins ... ascribe to the providence of God.”²⁵ Wesley continues to point out that divine providence not only extends to all persons, all things and all places²⁶, it also extends to all ages, for “no duration is long or short” before

²⁰ John Wesley, “Sermon 37: The Nature of Enthusiasm,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1987), §28, p. 56-57; John Wesley, “Sermon 54: On Eternity,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley, §20, p. 372; John Wesley, “Sermon 67: On Divine Providence,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley, §26, p. 547-8.

²¹ John Wesley, “Sermon 67: Divine On Providence,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley, §26.

²² Augustine, *Confessions*, III.xi, quoted in John Wesley, “Sermon 37: The Nature of Enthusiasm,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley, §28.

²³ Wesley, “Sermon 37: The Nature of Enthusiasm,” §28.

²⁴ Wesley, “Sermon 67: Divine On Providence,” §26.

²⁵ Wesley, “Sermon 37: The Nature of Enthusiasm,” §28.

²⁶ Cf. Wesley, “Sermon 67: Divine On Providence,” §26.

God.²⁷ Hence, Wesley further expands Augustine's words on divine providence to geography, history and time.

1.2 On God's Governance

Second, regarding God's governance, Wesley proclaims, "The true God is governor of all things ... throughout all ages."²⁸ Wesley continues, "He is the Lord and disposer of the whole creation, and every part of it."²⁹ Concerning the method of God's governance, Wesley believes that we know nothing but Augustine's "[God] presidest over each creature as if it were the universe, and over the universe as over each individual creature."³⁰ Thus, Wesley apparently believes that no other description could describe God's governance better than Augustine's words. He believes that God governs this universe and every creature through His providence.

1.3 On Human Condition

Third, regarding the human condition, Wesley believes that humans are inevitably ignorant and inclined to err. Wesley used "*humanum est errare et nesaire*" ("to be ignorant of many things, and to mistake in some, is the necessary condition of humanity")³¹ to describe the human condition. As pointed out by Rupert E. Davis, Wesley probably made up the "*humanum est errare et nesaire*" phrase "from several sources, including Cicero, Seneca and Augustine."³² Thus, Wesley's concept of the human helpless condition might have been

²⁷ John Wesley, "Sermon 54: On Eternity," in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley, §20.

²⁸ John Wesley, "Sermon 77: Spiritual Worship," in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 3, *Sermons III: 71-114*, by John Wesley, I.8.

²⁹ *Ibid.*

³⁰ *Ibid.*

³¹ John Wesley, "Sermon 39: Catholic Spirit," in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley, §I.4; Cf. John Wesley, "A Short Address to the Inhabitants of Ireland: Occasioned by some late Occurrences," in Rupert E. Davies, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 9, *The Methodist Societies: History, Nature, and Design*, by John Wesley (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1989), §15.

³² Davies, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 9, *The Methodist Societies: History, Nature, and Design*, by John Wesley, 285n9.

influenced by Augustine.

1.4 On God's Works on Believers

Fourth, regarding God's works on believers, Wesley identifies with Augustine in three aspects. Firstly, regarding the things we have, Wesley agrees with Augustine that everything we have except our sins is given by God freely, as he writes in hymn 323 "Whate'er I have was freely given / Nothing but sin I call my own"³³. These lines, according to Beckerlegge, seem to be a paraphrase of Augustine's *Soliloqueis*, c.xv "For if there is anything of good, whatever great or small, it is thy gift, and there is nothing of our own but evil."³⁴

Secondly, Wesley also agrees with Augustine that God is our healer, and he further concludes that God is our "all in all"³⁵. He writes, "The ruins of my soul repair / And make my heart a house of prayer."³⁶ This sentence, according to Beckerlegge, seems to be Wesley's paraphrase of Augustine's *Confessions*, I.v: "Narrow is the mansion of my souls; enlarge thou it, that thou mayest enter in. It is ruinous; repair thou it."³⁷ Besides that, Wesley also writes,

Jesu, my all in all thou art,
My rest in toil, my ease in pain;
The med'cine of my broken heart,
In war my peace, in loss my gain;
My smile beneath the tyrant's frown,
In shame my glory and my crown.³⁸

Again, Beckerlegge claims that these lines seem to be Wesley's paraphrase of Augustine's *Soliloquies*, c.ii: "I am ill, and cry out for a physician; I am blind, and hasten to the light; I am dead, and sigh for life. Thou art the physician, thou the light, thou art life. Jesus of Nazareth, have pity on me!"³⁹

³³ Oliver A. Beckerlegge, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 7, *A Collection of Hymns for the Use of The People Called Methodists*, by John Wesley (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1983), #323ll.21-22..

³⁴ "Quoniam si quid boni est parvum vel magnum, donum tuum est, et nostrum non est nisi malum." (Ibid., 479n21-22.)

³⁵ Ibid., #201ll.13.

³⁶ Ibid., #179ll.17-18.

³⁷ Ibid., #179n17-18.

³⁸ Ibid., #201ll.13-18.

³⁹ Ibid., #201n13-18.

Lastly, since God is “my all in all”⁴⁰, then He is the “soul of my soul”⁴¹. Wesley might have quoted this phrase from Blackmore’s “An Ode to the Divine Being,” ii.3-4: “My portion, my reward immense, soul of my soul, my life, my all”, and Meditations of Saint Theresa: “God is the soul of my soul”, which, according to Beckerlegge, was also used by Augustine.⁴² God is our all in all, soul of our soul, thus we can only find rest in Him alone, as Wesley wrote, “At rest, till it finds rest in thee.”⁴³ Again, Wesley might have quoted these words from Augustine’s *Confessions*, I.i: “Thou hast made us for thyself; and our heart cannot rest till it rests in thee.”⁴⁴

1.5 On Ethics

Fifth, in the aspect of ethics, regarding “*officious* lies” or good intended lies, Wesley points out that although many pious and educated writers claimed “*officious* lies” as sinless and even commendable, he believes that the Bible is strongly against “*officious* lies”.⁴⁵ He comes to this conclusion by examining Rom 3: 7-8.⁴⁶ He fully agrees and quotes Augustine’s *Contra Mendacium (Against Lying)*, chap. 15: “I would not tell a lie, no, not to save the souls of the whole world.”⁴⁷ He believes that Augustine’s teaching not to say any good intended lie is scriptural, as reflected in Rom. 3:8.⁴⁸

Therefore, in the aspects of God’s providence, governance and works on believers, as

⁴⁰ Ibid., #2011l.13.

⁴¹ Ibid., #331l.21.

⁴² Ibid., #331n21.

⁴³ Ibid., #335l.6.

⁴⁴ “*Fecisti nes ad te; et irrequietum est in te.*” (Ibid., #335n6.)

⁴⁵ John Wesley, “Sermon 90: An Israelite Indeed,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 3, *Sermons III: 71-114*, by John Wesley, II.3; Cf. John Wesley, “A Farther Appeal to Men of Reason and Religion, Part II,” in Gerald R. Cragg, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 11, *The Appeals to Men of Reason and Religion and Certain Related Open Letters*, by John Wesley (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1989), §24; John Wesley, “A Letter to the Right Revered the Lord Bishop of Gloucester,” in Gerald R. Cragg, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 11, *The Appeals to Men of Reason and Religion and Certain Related Open Letters*, by John Wesley, V.27.

⁴⁶ Wesley, “Sermon 90: An Israelite Indeed,” II.3.

⁴⁷ J. P. Migne, ed., *Patrologiae Cursus Completus: Series Latina* (Paris, 1878-90), XL. 540, quoted in John Wesley, “A Farther Appeal to Men of Reason and Religion, Part II,” §24; in John Wesley, “A Letter to the Right Revered the Lord Bishop of Gloucester,” V.27; in John Wesley, “Sermon 90: An Israelite Indeed,” II.3.

⁴⁸ Wesley, “A Farther Appeal to Men of Reason and Religion, Part II,” §24, 236n8.

well as human condition and ethics, Wesley fully agrees with Augustine.

1.6 On Pelagius

However, Wesley does not agree with Augustine in all issues, as commented by Outler, “Traditionalist though he was, Wesley was also critical of traditional condemnations of those he recognized as kindred spirits in one degree or another”⁴⁹ such as Montanus and Pelagius.⁵⁰ Wesley disagrees with Augustine’s condemnations on Pelagius as heretic. He claims that he “verily believe[s] the real heresy of Pelagius was neither more nor less than this, the holding that Christians may by the grace of God (not without it; that I take to be a mere slander) ‘go on to perfection’; or, in other words, ‘fulfil the law of Christ’.”⁵¹ In other words, he believes that Augustine was wrong in condemning Pelagius as heretic.

In this matter, Outler believes that Wesley had made a mistake in defending Pelagius. He pointed out that Wesley had failed to notice the key difference among Pelagius and him, that “for Pelagius, prevenience is not emphasized, whereas for Wesley the Spirit’s initiative is the dynamic essence of all grace.”⁵²

Anyway, we need to have more studies to determine the accurateness of Outler’s statement. However, this is not the focus of this study. The point here is to highlight the fact that Wesley did not accept Augustine’s teachings blindly, but through critical reflection.

1.7 Conclusion

This chapter has shown that Wesley did read Augustine’s works and used them in his works, and it was proven that he agreed with Augustine at least on these topics: God’s providence, God’s governance, human conditions, God’s works on believers, and ethics. It

⁴⁹ John Wesley, “Sermon 68: The Wisdom of God’s Counsels,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley, §9n31.

⁵⁰ *Ibid.*, §9.

⁵¹ *Ibid.*

⁵² *Ibid.*, §9n32.

might also be acceptable for us to suggest that Wesley had read Augustine's works widely and comprehensively, since he not only agreed with Augustine on some topics, but also criticized Augustine on other topics, such as on Pelagius. So we should not deny the possibility that Wesley might also have used or criticized Augustine's works or be influenced by him indirectly on other topics, including his concept of prevenient grace, which is the interest of this study. In other words, it is quite likely that a relationship exists between Augustine's and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace, and the task of this study is to ascertain the existence of this relationship. Hence, this chapter has justified the author's approach of study, which is to compare Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace in order to find out whether any relationship exists between them.

CHAPTER 2

AUGUSTINE DOCTRINE OF GRACE: A BRIEF LITERATURE REVIEW

Before we can compare Augustine's and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace, we need to study each concept first. In order to study Augustine's concept of prevenient grace more systematically and, if possible, more comprehensively, a framework (that is a system and flow of study) is needed. Although Augustine did discuss his doctrine of grace, which included his concept of prevenient grace systematically, he did not systematise his doctrine of grace into a conceptual and operational framework. Thus, there is no framework provided by Augustine himself. However, Warfield and Burns have constructed their frameworks respectively for Augustine's doctrine of grace.⁵³ In this chapter, the author will first introduce their frameworks, then based on their frameworks to propose an appropriate framework to study Augustine's concept of prevenient grace.

2.1 Benjamin B. Warfield

In studying Augustine's doctrine of grace (or Warfield's term theology of grace), Warfield develops a framework which comprises four components or aspects – “the necessity of grace to man,” the nature of grace, “the effects of grace,” and “the means of grace.”⁵⁴ In his work, Warfield firstly identifies that Augustine's doctrine of grace is built on the basic tenet of his whole theology – “God as the immanent and vital spirit in whom all things live and move and have their being.”⁵⁵ In other words, all creatures have to depend on God completely for their being, living and doing. Man, especially after the fall, cannot will and opt for good by their own.⁵⁶ We can only will and opt for good with the help from God

⁵³ See *Augustine through the Ages: An Encyclopedia*, s.v. “Grace,” and Warfield, “Introductory Essay on Augustin and the Pelagian Controversy,” 70-77.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*, 70-75.

⁵⁵ *Ibid.*, 70.

⁵⁶ See *ibid.*, 71-72.

through His grace. His grace is “in Jesus Christ, conveyed to us by the Holy Spirit and evidenced by the love that He sheds abroad in our hearts.”⁵⁷ In short, divine grace is God’s assistance to us to will and opt for good in Jesus Christ through the Holy Spirit.

Therefore, from the condition of man, divine grace is necessary for us to will and opt for good. This is what Augustine means, according to Warfield, “the necessity of grace to man.”⁵⁸ Since man cannot will and opt for good by themselves, then we need God to give us grace first in order to initiate and enable us to will and opt for good.⁵⁹ According to Warfield, the initiative of God in giving man divine grace attributes prevenience to the nature of divine grace.⁶⁰ Since divine grace is “prevenient,” then it must be “gratuitous,” that is, given to man not according to man’s preceding merits but “on the ground of God’s infinite mercy and undeserved favour.”⁶¹ Since divine grace is gratuitous, then it must be sovereign, that it is given to some and not others solely according to God’s pleasure.⁶² Prevenience, gratuity and sovereignty ascribe to the nature of divine grace.

This prevenient, gratuitous and sovereign divine grace is given by God on high to some individuals (lower being), thus its effects – justification, sanctification and perseverance – are “irresistible” and “indefectible”.⁶³ Those God has given grace will surely repent, regenerate and persevere to the end.⁶⁴ Although divine grace operates in different steps, it is “a constant efflux from God,” not “a series of disconnected divine gift.”⁶⁵ By integrating his doctrine of the Church into the doctrine of grace, Augustine asserts that although God is able to convey His grace without any means, He has chosen the Church (visible and invisible) and baptism as the means of grace.⁶⁶ Thus he has to come to a conclusion that baptism is

⁵⁷ Ibid., 70.

⁵⁸ Ibid., 71.

⁵⁹ Ibid., 73.

⁶⁰ See *ibid.*, 73.

⁶¹ Ibid., 73.

⁶² See *ibid.*, 73.

⁶³ Ibid., 73-74.

⁶⁴ See *ibid.*, 73-74.

⁶⁵ Ibid., 73.

⁶⁶ See *ibid.*, 75.

necessary for salvation.⁶⁷

2.2 J. Patout Burns

On the other hand, Burns' framework consists of three big components – “philosophical foundations”, “scriptural principles” and “the history of grace”.⁶⁸ In other words, he attempts to analyse and study Augustine's doctrine of grace (or in his term theme of grace) from three perspectives – philosophical, biblical and operational. From philosophical perspective, Augustine adapts “Neoplatonic theory of emanation.”⁶⁹ According to this theory, “being, power, and even operation are continuously communicated from the highest being to the lower levels of a hierarchically ordered universe.”⁷⁰ Augustine injected a Christian element into this theory of emanation, suggesting that the highest being refers to God, and the lower beings refer to men and angels.⁷¹ God continuously influences human and angels through the operation and dwelling of the Holy Spirit.⁷² This divine influence is what ‘grace’ means.

From biblical sources, Augustine has drawn out some principles to support his adaptation of Neoplatonic theory of emanation in constructing his doctrine of grace. Burns discussed Augustine's Scriptural principles in five aspects – “identity, necessity, gratuity, efficacy, and social role.”⁷³ In the aspect of identity, divine grace operates in two forms – “Light in the mind” and “Love in the will”.⁷⁴ The former refers to the “Word of God who rules and guides the creature in understanding and judging,” and the latter refers to the indwelling of the Holy Spirit.⁷⁵

In the aspect of necessity, Burns discussed the necessity of grace from two

⁶⁷ Ibid., 75-76.

⁶⁸ *Augustine through the Ages: An Encyclopedia*, s.v. “Grace.”

⁶⁹ Ibid.

⁷⁰ Ibid.

⁷¹ See *ibid.*

⁷² See *ibid.*

⁷³ Ibid.

⁷⁴ Ibid.

⁷⁵ Ibid.

perspectives. First, for humans “grace is necessary for good willing and working,” especially after the fall human beings become sinners and lose the power to will and opt for good.⁷⁶ Second, for the Holy Spirit (the divine love), His operation “was restricted to the sacraments and participants of that communion,” thus Church sacraments “were necessary for salvation.”⁷⁷

In the aspect of gratuity, Burns identified the point according to Augustine that God’s grace is necessarily gratuitous in His creation, providence and election of man to his salvation, perseverance and glorification.⁷⁸ Thus, God’s grace is gratuitous in every aspect.

In the aspect of efficacy, Burns pointed out in Augustine’s teaching, God’s grace is efficacious,⁷⁹ which means that God’s grace will certainly cause man to act according to His desired end. The efficacy of this divine grace is secured in two ways, namely, through divine “providential control over the environment of choice, coupled with the exhaustive divine knowledge of the dispositions of the human heart,” and through the “interior operation of the Holy Spirit which makes preaching, exhortation, and correction effective.”⁸⁰ Through these two ways, divine grace acts upon human, moving them to work together with it to God’s desired end.

The efficacy of divine grace is not only present in the individual, but also in the “creation and development of society.”⁸¹ This is the social role of the divine grace. Divine grace, operated by the indwelling of the Holy Spirit in individual Christians, joins angels, saints in heaven and Christians on earth to form a new community.⁸² This new community, known as the invisible Church, is the core of the visible Church.⁸³ Christians in the invisible Church share the “common love of God and mutual love of one another.”⁸⁴ With this love,

⁷⁶ Ibid.

⁷⁷ Ibid.

⁷⁸ See *ibid.*

⁷⁹ Ibid.

⁸⁰ Ibid.

⁸¹ Ibid.

⁸² Ibid.

⁸³ Ibid.

⁸⁴ Ibid.

they accept the Church attendees into the community of the local Church, hoping that they will convert; and with this love, they bring the unbelievers to Christ.⁸⁵ This love binds Christians together into unity of the Church, against the “divisive forces of human sinfulness.”⁸⁶

After discussing the scriptural principles of Augustine’s doctrine of grace, Burns continued to discuss Augustine’s doctrine of grace from operational perspective, which he called the history of grace. The history of grace refers to God’s grace in the various steps of “the history of humanity” – “from creation and fall through law and faith to grace and glory.”⁸⁷ Augustine applied “the history of humanity” as an analogy to “the life of an individual”.⁸⁸ He identified that, in the life of an individual, the process of salvation comprised four stages – repentance, regeneration, sanctification and glorification.⁸⁹ Divine grace operates in these four stages in the forms of “divine law,” “divine love,” “gift of perseverance” and “fullness of grace.”⁹⁰

2.3 Comments

Although Warfield and Burns analyzed Augustine’s doctrine of grace with different frameworks, basically all the components of their frameworks and the contents of their studies can be reorganized into three big components – definition, nature and operation of grace. Both Warfield and Burn’s findings for Augustine’s definition of grace, both philosophical and Scriptural, can be categorized into the definition of grace. Warfield’s study on the necessity and nature of grace, as well as some contents of his study on the effect of grace to man, can be put under the nature of grace. Burns’ study on the philosophical foundations and Scriptural principles of Augustine’s doctrine of grace can be grouped under

⁸⁵ Ibid.

⁸⁶ Ibid.

⁸⁷ Ibid.

⁸⁸ Ibid.

⁸⁹ See *ibid.*

⁹⁰ Ibid.

the nature of grace as well. Finally, Warfield's study on the means of grace and some contents of his study on the effect of grace, as well as Burn's study on the history of grace, can be put under the operation of grace. Thus, it is justifiable to study Augustine's doctrine of grace, particularly the prevenience of grace, from these three aspects – definition, nature and operation.

Despite the different terms and the frameworks used, as a whole both Warfield and Burns' studies on Augustine's grace have similar outcome. Both of them agree that philosophically, Augustine's doctrine of grace is built on the Platonic theory of emanation. They also agree that divine grace is necessary for human salvation; that divine grace is gratuitous, prevenient, sovereign and irresistible in its nature (though Burns did not use the terms prevenient, sovereign and irresistible, he did explain these concepts in different ways). In addition, they also agree that divine grace is a constant flow of gift from God to man, which operates in every step of human salvation.

In discussing Augustine's concept of the prevenience of grace, Warfield and Burn treated prevenient grace as one of the natures of grace. While on one hand, it is right that the prevenience of grace is one of the natures of grace, on the other hand, the prevenience of grace is not only a nature of grace, but also an important nature of grace that pervades Augustine's doctrine of grace. This will be studied in the next chapter of this work.

2.4 Conclusion

From the examination above, we see that both Warfield and Burns provided us with two systematic frameworks for studying Augustine's doctrine of grace. These two frameworks can be restructured into a combined framework, which consists of definition, nature and operation of divine grace. In the next chapter, the author will use this framework to study Augustine's concept of prevenient grace.

CHAPTER 3

AUGUSTINE’S CONCEPT OF PREVENIENT GRACE: A BRIEF STUDY

The prevenient nature of grace is not a small portion of Augustine’s doctrine of grace. In fact, it is an important theme that pervades every part of Augustine’s doctrine of grace. In this chapter, the author will study Augustine’s concept of prevenient grace by using the framework proposed in the previous chapter, which consists of definition, nature and operation of prevenient grace.

3.1 Definition of Prevenient Grace

What is prevenient grace in Augustine’s doctrine of grace? Before defining prevenient grace, it is necessary to define the term ‘grace’ as Augustine understood it. Augustine did not write a passage to specifically define God’s grace, but he did explain what God’s grace was through his discussion in his writings. To Augustine, God’s grace, or divine grace, is the gift of the Holy Spirit to men.⁹¹ In fact, to Augustine, divine grace is not only “the gift of the Holy Ghost,” but as according to II Corinthians 3:6, it itself is God’s “life-giving Spirit”⁹² or in his other term, “vivifying Spirit.”⁹³ Besides these definitions, Augustine also defined divine grace as “divine aid,”⁹⁴ or more specifically “assisting grace of our crucified Saviour Christ, and the gift of His Spirit.”⁹⁵ Among other definitions of divine grace Augustine came out with his study of Scripture which includes perfect strength in weaknesses⁹⁶ and

⁹¹ See Augustine, “A Treatise on the Spirit and the Letter,” chap. 5, in *NPNF1-05. St. Augustin: Anti-Pelagian Writings*, ed. Philip Schaff [book on-line] (Grand Rapids: Christian Classics Ethereal Library, 2004, accessed 2 January 2005); available from <http://www.ccel.org/ccel/schaff/npnf105.html>; Internet; p. 200. All following Augustine’s writings, unless indicated otherwise, are taken from *NPNF1-05*.

⁹² *Ibid.*, chap. 32, in p. 221. See also chaps. 6, 8, 34, 42 in pp. 201, 203, 222, 228. See also Augustine, “A Work on the Proceedings of Pelagius,” chap. 20, in p. 356; Augustine, “A Treatise on Grace and Free Will,” chap. 24, in p. 744; Augustine, “On the Grace of Christ,” chap. 14, in p. 401.

⁹³ Augustine, “A Work on the Proceedings of Pelagius,” chap. 21, in p. 357.

⁹⁴ Augustine, “On the Grace of Christ,” chap. 16, in p. 402. See also chap. 9, in p. 397.

⁹⁵ Augustine, “A Treatise on Nature and Grace,” chap. 70, in p. 296.

⁹⁶ II Corinthians 12:9, quoted in Augustine, “On the Grace of Christ,” chap. 13, in p.400.

“teaching.”⁹⁷ In summary, as according to Augustine, divine grace is God’s aid in Jesus Christ in the form of Holy Spirit and teaching.

After defining God’s grace in Augustine’s theology, it is appropriate to define the term ‘prevenient’. Besides using the term prevenient, Augustine also used the term “preventing grace” as an alternative to “prevenient grace”. Although Augustine did not define the term prevenient grace directly, it was obvious from his writings that to him prevenient meant God has taken the initiative in men’s salvation,⁹⁸ and men have nothing to do at all to gain salvation; everything was simply God’s action.⁹⁹ He used the verb “prevent” to describe the same concept for prevenient (adjective).¹⁰⁰ In this context, “prevent” carries the same meaning with “precede” and can be used interchangeably.

Hence, according to Augustine, prevenient grace means God’s gift of assistance in Jesus Christ through the Holy Spirit, which is prior to men’s merits; this gift is given totally on the ground of God’s mercy, not depending on men’s merits. In other words, prevenient grace means God’s gift to man beforehand. This will be further explained in the part of the nature and operation of prevenient grace.

3.2 The Nature of Prevenient Grace

Prevenient grace is God’s gift in Christ to man, which is conveyed through the Holy Spirit. It is the work and gift of the Holy Trinity to man prior to man’s merits. God is the giver and man is the receiver. These are two important aspects in prevenient grace – without the giver there is no prevenient grace, and without the receiver the prevenient grace is redundant. Thus these two important aspects are appropriate approaches to studying the nature of prevenient grace. Among these two approaches, it is appropriate to start with the aspect of God, since the foremost principle or basic tenet of Augustine’s doctrine of grace, as

⁹⁷ Augustine, “On the Grace of Christ,” chap. 14, in p. 401.

⁹⁸ See Augustine, “A Treatise on the Merits and Forgiveness of Sins, and on the Baptism of Infants,” I.29, p. 111; Augustine, “A Treatise on Grace and Free Will,” chap. 44, in p. 761.

⁹⁹ See Augustine, “A Treatise Against Two Letters of Pelagians,” II.21, p. 665.

¹⁰⁰ See *Ibid.*

pointed out by Burns and Warfield, is the “Neoplatonic theory of emanation,”¹⁰¹ a theory that identifies “God as the immanent and vital spirit in whom all things live and move and have their being.”¹⁰² In other words, God is the origin and source of grace, in which all other beings can live and move.

3.2.1 The Giver – God

With Neoplatonic theory of emanation as the underlying proposition, Augustine discussed the grace of God, particularly in soteriology. He adapted this proposition into his explanation of the Scriptures. Four principles on prevenient grace can be drawn from his explanation on divine grace. In this section, the author will discuss the principles on the nature of prevenient grace from the aspect of the Giver.

The first principle is that prevenient grace is God’s gratuitous and sovereign gift to man. Warfield has argued that the very nature of prevenient of grace must necessarily lead to the gratuitous nature of grace.¹⁰³ By gratuitous it means divine grace is given freely to man,¹⁰⁴ according to “the good pleasure of His will.”¹⁰⁵ Since prevenient grace is given according to God’s will, then it must be sovereign. Prevenient grace must also lead to sovereignty of grace, as Augustine writes, “God’s grace is prevenient in His choosing them [(men)].”¹⁰⁶ God has chosen man first before man chooses God,¹⁰⁷ and He chooses those He has “predestined and called according to [His] divine purpose.”¹⁰⁸ “The good pleasure of His will” and “according to [His] divine purpose” refer to the sovereignty of God in giving His prevenient grace to man. Prevenient grace is God’s free gift to man according to “the good pleasure of His will” and His “divine purpose”, thus it must be gratuitous and sovereign.

¹⁰¹ *Augustine through the Ages: An Encyclopedia*, s.v. “Grace.”

¹⁰² Warfield, “Introductory Essay on Augustin and the Pelagian Controversy,” p. 70.

¹⁰³ *Ibid.*, p. 73.

¹⁰⁴ See Augustine, “A Treatise on Nature and Grace,” chap. 4, in p. 256.

¹⁰⁵ Augustine, “A Treatise on the Predestination of the Saints,” 1.35, 37, in pp. 830, 831; Augustine, “A Treatise on the Gift of Perseverance,” chaps. 15, 16, 28, in pp. 846, 854.

¹⁰⁶ Augustine, “A Treatise on Grace and Free Will,” chap.38, in p.755.

¹⁰⁷ See *ibid.*

¹⁰⁸ Augustine, “On the Grace of Christ,” chap.13, in p. 400.

The second principle is that prevenient grace is God's gift in Jesus Christ conveyed by the Holy Spirit to man. In Augustine's doctrine of grace, from the very start of divine grace and to its perfection must be in Jesus Christ and through the Holy Spirit,¹⁰⁹ because salvation is only in Jesus Christ¹¹⁰ and the works of the Holy Spirit.¹¹¹ In other words, God's gift is only in Jesus Christ and not beyond it, and the Holy Spirit is the only agent of divine grace.

The third principle is that the very nature of prevenient grace is its being 'prevenient.' Augustine writes, "His mercy anticipates us."¹¹² In other words, God has prepared His divine grace in advance for man. The very first step of man to believe, that is, the first faith man has, is the prevenient gift of God, not from man himself. In respect to this Augustine writes, "the very will by which we believe is reckoned as a gift of God."¹¹³ He also writes, "by His mercy even faith itself is bestowed."¹¹⁴ Nothing of man is originally his; all man has is the gift of God in advance. Thus God's grace is prevenient.

The fourth principle is that prevenient grace is not another grace of God or a separated grace from subsequent grace. Both prevenient grace and subsequent grace are not two different graces of God, but are the very same grace of God that works in different stages in the process of salvation.¹¹⁵ Prevenient grace is the initiative grace that initiates the process of salvation, whereas the subsequent grace assists us in the remaining process of salvation to its perfection. Thus, Warfield termed prevenient grace as operating grace, which means God's sole action; and subsequent grace as co-operating grace, which requires man's participation.¹¹⁶ However, Warfield reminded us that even the ability of man to participate in

¹⁰⁹ See Augustine, "On Original Sin," chap. 29, in p. 443; Augustine, "A Treatise on Rebuke and Grace," chaps. 2, 15, in pp. 767, 776.

¹¹⁰ See Augustine, "On Original Sin," chaps. 29, 30, 31, in pp. 443-444; Augustine, "A Treatise on Rebuke and Grace," chap. 3, in p. 767; Augustine, "A Treatise on Nature and Grace," chaps. 20, 21, pp. 264-265.

¹¹¹ See Augustine, "A Treatise on Rebuke and Grace," chap. 2, in p. 767; Augustine, "On the Grace of Christ," chap. 14, in p. 401.

¹¹² Augustine, "A Treatise on Nature and Grace," chap. 35, in p. 274.

¹¹³ Augustine, "A Treatise on the Spirit and the Letter," chap. 60, in p. 245.

¹¹⁴ Augustine, "A Treatise Against Two Letters of the Pelagians," IV.10, in p. 696; see Augustine, "A Treatise on Grace and Free Will," chap. 17, in p. 739.

¹¹⁵ See Augustine, "A Treatise on Nature and Grace," chap. 35, in p. 247.

¹¹⁶ See Warfield, "Introductory Essay on Augustin and the Pelagian Controversy," p. 73.

the process of salvation is also the gift of divine grace.¹¹⁷ In other words, the ability of man to participate with the subsequent grace is firstly given by God in advance. This is prevenient grace. Subsequent grace in fact is the extension or part of prevenient grace. Hence, it is obvious that prevenience is not only a characteristic of divine grace in the first step of salvation, but it is also a quality that permeates the process of salvation.

Among these four principles of the nature of prevenient grace, the first, third and fourth prove that prevenience is not only one of the natures of divine grace, but it is also interrelated with other natures of divine grace and is the foundation for the subsequent grace. If divine grace is not prevenient, then it cannot be gratuitous and sovereign; since divine grace is gratuitous and sovereign, it must be prevenient. As a result of this, prevenient grace must be gratuitous and sovereign, or else it cannot be prevenient. On the other hand, the grace of God must be prevenient in the first place and only then can man participate in the subsequent grace. Thus it is proven that prevenient is interrelated with other natures of grace and is the foundation for subsequent grace.

The second principle of the nature of prevenient grace sets the boundary for the operation of the divine grace. The grace of God, from its very start to its completion, must operate only in Jesus Christ by the Holy Spirit.

In conclusion, these four principles of the nature of prevenient grace of the Giver are the basic principles for the other principles in relation to man and in the operation of grace, which will be discussed in the following sections.

3.2.2 The Receiver – Man

God is the Giver of grace and man is the receiver. Thus, besides discussing the nature of prevenient grace in the aspect of the Giver, it is necessary also to discuss it in the aspect of the receiver. Two principles can be drawn from Augustine's doctrine of grace regarding his

¹¹⁷ See *ibid.*, p. 74.

concept of prevenient grace.

First, prevenient grace is necessary for salvation. As argued by Warfield, according to Augustine, although after the fall our faculty of free will remains neutral, the active agent that uses the faculty of free will (that is man) is corrupted by original sin and sin he has committed, thus he is not able to use his faculty of free will for good purpose.¹¹⁸ In other words, since every man is corrupted by original sin and the sin he commits, no man is able to participate in the process of salvation. Thus, divine grace is needed, even Adam also needed grace to remain his sinless state before the fall.¹¹⁹ After the fall, every man needs divine grace for his salvation, for “without [divine grace men] do absolutely no good.”¹²⁰ Every good we desire and perform is caused by God, for “without Him we are able to do nothing actually, we are able neither to begin nor to perfect” our salvation.¹²¹ Man can only “shun evil and do good” with the assistance of divine grace, for “none can [shun evil and do good] without the Spirit of grace.”¹²² To conclude, it is correct to say that since man is not able to stop evil and to will and perform good, prevenient grace is necessary to initiate the process of salvation, or else man will surely perish in his sin.

Second, prevenient grace is given freely to man, which requires no man’s own merits. Augustine writes, “This grace [(divine grace)]...is not rendered for any merits, but is given *gratis*, on account of which it is also called grace.”¹²³ Prevenient grace is given on the ground of God’s grace, thus it is necessarily free to man. Since it is free and sinful man can not do anything to earn salvation, no merits can precede grace. Augustine writes that “men have no prevenient merits for deserving [justification],”¹²⁴ for “the very will by which we

¹¹⁸ See *ibid.*, p. 71-72.

¹¹⁹ See Augustine, “A Treatise on Rebuke and Grace,” chaps. 29-32, in pp. 786-789.

¹²⁰ *Ibid.*, chap.3, in p. 767.

¹²¹ Augustine, “A Treatise Against Two Letters of the Pelagians,” II.21, in pp. 664-665.

¹²² Augustine, “A Treatise on Rebuke and Grace,” chap. 2, in p. 767.

¹²³ Augustine, “A Treatise on Nature and Grace,” chap.4, in 256.

¹²⁴ Augustine, “A Treatise on the Merits and Forgiveness of Sins, and on the Baptism of Infants,” I.29, in p. 111.

believe is reckoned as a gift of God.”¹²⁵ On one hand, God’s grace is prevenient, thus no prevenient merits of man are needed. On the other hand, because sinful man cannot have merits to earn salvation, God’s grace must be prevenient to initiate the process of salvation.

As a sinner, man is not able to stop evil and do good, thus prevenient grace is needed to enable man to do so. Since divine grace is prevenient, it requires no merits of man to precede it; and since man is not able to stop evil and do good, then divine grace must be prevenient to initiate the process of salvation. It is obvious then that prevenient grace is God’s free gift in advance, which is necessary for man to be saved.

3.2.3 Conclusion

In conclusion, in respect to the Giver, the prevenient grace of God is prevenient, gratuitous, sovereign and free to man, which is given by God the Father, founded only in Jesus Christ, and transmitted by the Holy Spirit – it is the gift of the Holy Trinity. In the aspect of the receiver, prevenient grace is needed for salvation, and no merits of man can precede prevenient grace.

However, how does the prevenient grace of God operate and affect the man He has chosen according to His purpose? This question will be discussed in the following section.

3.3 Operation of Prevenient Grace

Prevenient grace is God’s initiative gift in Jesus Christ, given by the Holy Spirit to chosen men for their salvation. In other words, the operation of prevenient grace is in fact the operation of the Holy Spirit Himself. The Holy Spirit operates in certain ways through certain means to make God’s prevenient grace work in man. Thus, the operation of prevenient grace can be studied in three aspects – the means, the effects and the scope of the operation.

¹²⁵ Augustine, “A Treatise on the Spirit and the Letter,” chap. 60, in p. 245. See also Augustine, “On the Grace of Christ,” chap. 27, in pp. 409-410; Augustine, “A Treatise on the Merits and Forgiveness of Sins, and on the Baptism of Infants,” I.62, in p. 134; Augustine, “A Treatise on Grace and Free Will,” chaps. 38, 44, in pp. 755, 761.

3.3.1 The Means of the Operation

What are the means of the operation of the Holy Spirit? Burns identifies the concept in Augustine's doctrine of grace that the Holy Spirit operates in two forms – "Light in the mind" and "Love in the will" – through four ways – "the giving of the divine Law," "the gift of divine Love" or "the indwelling of the Holy Spirit," "the gift of perseverance" and the "fullness of grace."¹²⁶ Warfield identifies that "the means of grace" in Augustine doctrine of grace is baptism by the Church.¹²⁷ However, all these various means and ways of the operation of the Holy Spirit can be put into two categories – external means and internal means. External means refer to means which are outside men but still affect men while internal means refer to means within men.

3.3.1.1 The External Means of Operation

What are the external means of operation? External means include the divine law, divine providence and the baptism by the Church. Augustine affirms the positive value of the divine law. He believes that divine law does not contradict with divine grace; indeed, divine law convicts us of our pride,¹²⁸ weakness¹²⁹ and sinfulness,¹³⁰ directs us to divine grace,¹³¹ and "lead[s] [us] to Christ."¹³² However, these purposes of the law can only be fulfilled by the assistance of the divine grace, for "without His assisting grace, the law is 'the letter which killeth.'"¹³³ With the assistance of divine grace through the operation of the "life-giving Spirit,"¹³⁴ the divine law can fulfil its tasks. Yet it should be borne in mind that divine law is not the same as divine grace;¹³⁵ for it is not the divine law that works as the divine grace, but

¹²⁶ *Augustine through the Ages: An Encyclopedia*, s.v. "Grace."

¹²⁷ Warfield, "Introductory Essay on Augustin and the Pelagian Controversy," p. 75.

¹²⁸ Augustine, "A Treatise on the Spirit and the Letter," chap. 15, in p. 208.

¹²⁹ *Ibid.*

¹³⁰ Augustine, "On Grace and Christ," chap. 9, in p. 397.

¹³¹ See Augustine, "On Grace of Christ," chap. 10, in p. 398.

¹³² Augustine, "A Treatise Concerning Man's Perfection in Righteousness," V. XI, in p. 314.

¹³³ Augustine, "A Treatise on the Spirit and the Letter," chap. 32, in p. 221, and more.

¹³⁴ *Ibid.*

¹³⁵ Augustine, "A Treatise Against Two Letters of the Pelagians," IV. 11, in p. 697.

the divine grace operates through the divine law.

How does divine grace work through the divine law? First, the giving of the law itself is the “operation of God’s grace.”¹³⁶ Then, “God’s grace and help...exists...in the law and teaching.”¹³⁷ Next, through the law and teaching, grace “helps us to feel our need of grace.”¹³⁸ Finally, through all these three steps divine law “fulfils its office as ‘schoolmaster,’ so terrifying the man as ‘to lead him to Christ,’ to give him his love,”¹³⁹ as written by Augustine,

God acts upon us by the incentives of our perceptions, to will and to believe, either externally by evangelical exhortation, where even the commands of the law also do something, if there so far admonish a man of his infirmity that he betakes himself to the grace that justifies by believing.¹⁴⁰

Divine grace works through divine law to enlighten our perceptions by admonishing us of our infirmities in order that we are enabled to will and believe in Christ.

In all the steps of the operation of divine grace through divine law, divine grace must be prevenient, for it precedes men’s merits – it starts its works before men have done anything. Man is not the factor – he cannot do anything to cause the divine grace to operate through the divine law. The Holy Spirit is the factor that causes divine grace to operate, and the operation of divine grace itself is the operation of the Holy Spirit. Thus, it is appropriate to say that the prevenient grace operates through divine law, and divine law is the means of the operation of the prevenient grace.

Besides divine law, divine providence is also one of the external means of prevenient grace. Augustine writes, “in all things [God] prevents us with His mercy. To yield our consent, indeed, to God’s summons, or to withhold it, is (as I have said) the function of our own will.”¹⁴¹

It is obvious that according to Augustine, for those He has chosen, God works through His

¹³⁶ Augustine, “A Treatise on the Spirit and the Letter,” chap. 32, in p. 221.

¹³⁷ Augustine, “On the Grace of Christ,” chap. 10, in p. 398.

¹³⁸ Ibid.

¹³⁹ Augustine, “A Treatise Concerning Man’s Perfection in Righteousness,” V. XI, in p. 314.

¹⁴⁰ Augustine, “A Treatise on the Spirit and the Letter,” chap. 60, in p. 245.

¹⁴¹ Ibid.

control over their environment in order that they will choose to abide by God's law. In Burns' words, "providential control over the environment of choice, coupled with the exhaustive divine knowledge of the dispositions of the human, [that is, internal means], could guarantee the salvific willing and working."¹⁴² The control over the environment to cause man to choose to believe is certainly the grace of God, and it is prevenient, for it is totally God's action, without any human element in it. Thus, it is appropriate to say that God's prevenient grace operates through His providence.

The baptism administered by the Catholic Church is another external means for divine grace. Warfield asserts that to Augustine, baptism is "absolutely necessary for salvation."¹⁴³ This is very true. Augustine did argue for the necessity of baptism for salvation in some of his writings. For example, in "A Treatise on the Merits and Forgiveness of Sins, and on the Baptism of Infants," Augustine writes, "baptism is nothing else than 'salvation,' and the sacrament of the body of Christ nothing else than 'life,'" therefore "neither salvation nor eternal life can be hoped for by any man without baptism and the Lord's body and blood."¹⁴⁴ This is one of the many evidences of Augustine teachings on the necessity of baptism.¹⁴⁵ As identified by Warfield, the necessity of baptism inevitably leads to Augustine's "doctrine of infant damnation."¹⁴⁶ According to this doctrine, since baptism is necessary for salvation, then those infants that died unbaptized do not have salvation.¹⁴⁷ Why is baptism necessary for salvation? It is because to Augustine, baptism is the only means for the remission of sins and

¹⁴² *Augustine through the Ages: An Encyclopedia*, s.v. "Grace."

¹⁴³ Warfield, "Introductory Essay on Augustin and the Pelagian Controversy," p. 75.

¹⁴⁴ Augustine, "A Treatise on the Merits and Forgiveness of Sins, and on the Baptism of Infants," I. 33, in p. 114-115.

¹⁴⁵ For other evidences please see Philip Schaff, ed. "Baptism, necessity of, for salvation," in Index to *NPNF1-05. St. Augustin: Anti-Pelagian Writings* [book on-line] (Grand Rapids: Christian Classics Ethereal Library, 2004, accessed 2 January 2005); available from <http://www.ccel.org/ccel/schaff/npnf105.html>; Internet; p.884.

¹⁴⁶ Warfield, "Introductory Essay on Augustin and the Pelagian Controversy," p. 76.

¹⁴⁷ See Augustine, "A Treatise on the Merits and Forgiveness of Sins, and on the Baptism of Infants," I. 21-23, in pp. 105-107, and whole bk. I.

regeneration.¹⁴⁸ Unbaptised adults are condemned due to their original and actual sins, but unbaptised infants are condemned due to their original sin, because they do not have actual sins.¹⁴⁹ Although Augustine's teachings on the necessity of baptism for salvation and the damnation of unbaptised infants may be questionable, it is obvious that to him that baptism is a means for God's grace. This grace is prevenient, because baptism is not men's merits to earn salvation, but is a means of grace prepared by God for remission of men's sins. Hence, it is appropriate to say that prevenient grace operates through baptism by the Church.

In conclusion, it is obvious that the divine law, environment and baptism by the Church are three external means for the operation of the Holy Spirit to cause God's prevenient grace to work in men. The former causes men to become aware of their needs for grace, and in the latter, there is remission of sins and regeneration.

3.3.1.2 The Internal Means of Operation

Besides operating through the external means, the Holy Spirit also operates through the internal means, which are means within men. These internal means include ability, will and deed.¹⁵⁰ The Holy Spirit indwells and operates within man in three steps: moves his ability, affects his will and affects his action.¹⁵¹ In other words, God enables us to will and to do good, as written by Augustine, "For God has not only given us the ability and aids it, but He further 'works in us to will and to do.'"¹⁵² From this statement, it is obvious that our ability to will and to do good is given by God and assisted by God – this is the grace of God. Then He also works within us to assist our will and deeds, so that we are able to will and do what is good, that is to

¹⁴⁸ For the evidences please see Philip Schaff, ed. "Baptism, regeneration in" and "Baptism, remission of sins in," in Index to *NPNF1-05. St. Augustin: Anti-Pelagian Writings* [book on-line] (Grand Rapids: Christian Classics Ethereal Library, 2004, accessed 2 January 2005); available from <http://www.ccel.org/ccel/schaff/npnf105.html>; Internet; p.884.

¹⁴⁹ See Philip Schaff, ed. "Infants, have no actual sins," in Index to *NPNF1-05. St. Augustin: Anti-Pelagian Writings* [book on-line] (Grand Rapids: Christian Classics Ethereal Library, 2004, accessed 2 January 2005); available from <http://www.ccel.org/ccel/schaff/npnf105.html>; Internet; p.889.

¹⁵⁰ See Augustine, "On the Grace of Christ," chap. 15, in p. 402.

¹⁵¹ Ibid.

¹⁵² Augustine, "On the Grace of Christ," chap. 26, in p. 408.

obey God’s command and to believe in Jesus. This grace is certainly prevenient, for “without which [men] do absolutely no good thing, whether in thought, or will and affection, or in action”¹⁵³ and “the desire of man...which is called good...does not begin without grace.”¹⁵⁴ Besides, Augustine also wrote “the very will by which we believe is reckoned as a gift of God,”¹⁵⁵ and “it is God who...works in man in the willing to believe.”¹⁵⁶ Moreover, even “to desire the help of grace is the beginning of grace.”¹⁵⁷ None of our ability, good will and good deeds, are of us. All are given by God preveniently, preceding our own efforts. We can not do anything to have gain ability to will and to do good, for it is merely the gift of God. Thus, it is right to say that prevenient grace operates through the internal means – man’s ability, will and deeds.

3.3.1.2 Conclusion

God’s prevenient grace operates through both the external and internal means to lead men into salvation. The operation of prevenient grace indeed is the operation of the Holy Spirit, since the Holy Spirit is the only agent for divine grace. No matter through which means God’s prevenient grace operates, it must be in Christ, since God’s grace can only be found in Christ. Prevenient grace must work through both means, so that it will affect men.

3.3.2 The Effects of the Operation

The effects of the operation of the prevenient grace can be clearly seen in the process of salvation. The process of salvation comprises three steps – justification, sanctification and perfection. For Augustine, according to the Bible, God’s grace operates throughout the whole process of salvation, from the beginning to its completion, from our justification throughout our sanctification to our glorification. He writes, “to begin, it is said ‘His mercy shall prevent

¹⁵³ Augustine, “A Treatise on Rebuke and Grace,” chap. 3, in p. 767.

¹⁵⁴ Augustine, “A Treatise Against Two Letters of the Pelagians,” II. 22, in p. 666.

¹⁵⁵ Augustine, “A Treatise on the Spirit and the Letter,” chap. 60, in p. 245.

¹⁵⁶ Ibid.

¹⁵⁷ Augustine, “A Treatise on Rebuke and Grace,” chap. 2, in p. 767.

me;’ to finish, it is said ‘His mercy shall follow me.’”¹⁵⁸ Thus, God’s grace initiates and completes the process of salvation.

The first step of the process of salvation, that is, our justification is the effect of the operation of God’s prevenient grace. We are justified “freely by [God’s] grace, through the redemption that is in Christ Jesus,”¹⁵⁹ for “(man’s) justification results from no merits of his own, but from the grace of God.”¹⁶⁰ Our justification is purely the work of God, preceding our merits and without our human element in it. Thus, the grace that justifies us is gratuitous, and at the same time it must be prevenient, for it precedes man’s efforts. Hence, it is appropriate to say our justification is the effect of prevenient grace, for without God’s grace working in us first, we cannot be saved.

The second step of the process of salvation, that is, sanctification, is also the effect of the operation of God’s prevenient grace. Although it is the subsequent or co-operating grace that operates in our sanctification (for “we are fellow-workers with Him who does the work,”¹⁶¹) this subsequent grace itself is also prevenient (for “we are fellow-workers with Him who does the works, because His mercy anticipates us.”¹⁶²) “His mercy anticipates us” – this is prevenient grace. Our sanctification is the work of God’s subsequent grace, but it can only be started by God’s prevenient grace. Although God’s subsequent grace is co-operating grace and given after prevenient or operating grace, it is given preceding man’s merits, thus subsequent grace itself is prevenient. Although Augustine distinguishes prevenient grace from subsequent grace, it is obvious that subsequent grace itself actually is prevenient grace. In fact, both prevenient grace and subsequent grace are not different graces – both of them are the same grace of God, but different aspects of that very grace. However, between these two aspects, the

¹⁵⁸ Augustine, “A Treatise Against Two Letters of the Pelagians,” II. 21, in p. 665. The quoted clauses in the quotation are Scriptural verses from Ps 54:10 and 23:6. See also Augustine, “A Treatise on Nature and Grace,” chap. 35, in p. 274; Augustine, “A Treatise Against Two Letters of Pelagians,” II. 22, in p. 665-66.

¹⁵⁹ Augustine, “A Treatise on the Spirit and the Letter,” chap. 21, in p. 213.

¹⁶⁰ Augustine, “A Treatise on the Merits and Forgiveness of Sins, and on the Baptism of Infants,” chap. 62, in p. 134.

¹⁶¹ Augustine, “A Treatise on Nature and Grace,” chap. 35, in p. 274.

¹⁶² Ibid.

prevenient nature of God's grace runs through the course of our sanctification.

The final step of the process of salvation, that is, our perfection, is also the effect of the operation of God's prevenient grace. Augustine writes, "He anticipates us that we may be called; He will follow us that we may be glorified."¹⁶³ Augustine also writes, "If God does not precede us, not only is it not perfected, but it is not even begun, from us."¹⁶⁴ It is then God's grace that precedes us, then only can we be perfected – this is God's prevenient grace, giving to us before we have or can do anything. It is God's prevenient grace that makes us perfect. Thus, it is appropriate to say that our perfection is the effect of God's prevenient grace.

Regarding the effects of the prevenient grace, Augustine asserts that God's prevenient grace must be effectual, that is, it must cause God's purposed action and outcome. Augustine writes, "For [man's] call, however, from heaven and his conversion by that great and most effectual call, God's grace was alone."¹⁶⁵ God's call for our conversion is the "great and most effectual call," and it is the call of God's grace alone. This call for conversion is the calling of God's prevenient grace, because it precedes men's merits.¹⁶⁶ In Augustine's doctrine of grace, God's grace is effectual – this is agreed by scholars such as Warfield, Burns and Stephen N. Filippo.¹⁶⁷

However, these scholars did not come to agreement on how God's grace becomes effectual. Warfield and Burns, who are reformed scholars, follow reformed tradition and assert that God's grace is irresistible.¹⁶⁸ Warfield came to this conclusion by studying Augustine's "A Treatise on Rebuke and Grace" chapters 40, 45 and "A Treatise on the Predestination of the Saints" chapter 13.¹⁶⁹ Burns, though he did not use the term 'irresistible', has suggested

¹⁶³ Ibid.

¹⁶⁴ Augustine, "A Treatise Against Two Letters of the Pelagians," II. 21, in p. 665.

¹⁶⁵ Augustine, "A Treatise on Grace and Free Will," chap. 12, in p. 735.

¹⁶⁶ See *ibid.*

¹⁶⁷ See Warfield, "Introductory Essay on Augustin and the Pelagian Controversy," p. 73-74; *Augustine through the Ages: An Encyclopedia*, s.v. "Grace"; Stephen N. Filippo, *Saint Augustine's Theology of Grace* [article on-line] (New York: Stephen N. Filippo, 1998; accessed 4 July 2005); available from <http://www.catholic.net/rcc/Periodicals/Faith/7-8-98/GRACE.html>; Internet.

¹⁶⁸ See Warfield, "Introductory Essay on Augustin and the Pelagian Controversy," p.74; *Augustine through the Ages: An Encyclopedia*, s.v. "Grace."

¹⁶⁹ Warfield, "Introductory Essay on Augustin and the Pelagian Controversy," p.74.

according to Augustine's adaptation to Neoplatonic theory of emanation that God's grace is the gift from God who is highest in the hierarchy to men who are in the lower hierarchic level.¹⁷⁰ However, Filippo, a Catholic scholar, opposes the teaching that God's grace is irresistible, and asserts, "Augustine does not say that grace is irresistible, but that it is very attractive in and of itself."¹⁷¹ Between these two parties, which party really reflects Augustine's teaching on the efficacy of God's grace?

Actually, both parties are right in certain respects. Filippo is right in saying that Augustine never said that God's grace was irresistible, because Augustine never used the term 'irresistible' to describe the effectiveness of God's grace. However, Warfield is also right with his conclusion that divine grace is irresistible, for Augustine has written, "It is not, then, to be doubted men's will cannot...withstand the will of God."¹⁷² He also writes, "This [justifying grace], which is hiddenly bestowed in human hearts by the Divine gift, [that is, the Holy Spirit], is rejected by no hard heart, because it is given for the sake of first taking away the hardness of the heart."¹⁷³ These writings of Augustine, though not using the term irresistible, apparently teach us that when God gives His grace to those He has chosen, they by no ways can resist God's grace. Thus, the grace of God is irresistible. Further, the Neoplatonic theory of emanation as pointed out by Burns certainly will lead to the conclusion that God's grace is irresistible. Hence, although Augustine did not use the term irresistible to describe the effectiveness of God's grace, he did teach us that God's grace is irresistible. This grace is prevenient, because it takes away the hardness of man's heart before he can come to Christ. Thus, it is right to say that in the aspect of effects, God's prevenient grace is irresistible.

It is obvious that God's prevenient grace, when it comes to us, must initiate and complete the process of our salvation, from our justification through sanctification to perfection. These effects must take place, thus God's prevenient grace must be irresistible.

¹⁷⁰ *Augustine through the Ages: An Encyclopedia*, s.v. "Grace."

¹⁷¹ Filippo, *Saint Augustine's Theology of Grace*.

¹⁷² Augustine, "A Treatise on Rebuke and Grace," chap. 45, in p. 796.

¹⁷³ Augustine, "A Treatise on the Predestination of the Saints," chap. 13, in p. 813.

3.3.3 The Scope of the Operation

God's grace is irresistible, but why are not all men saved? Augustine answers this question with his doctrine of predestination. Augustine writes, "[God's] predestination is the preparation for grace,"¹⁷⁴ and "grace is the effect of that predestination."¹⁷⁵ Augustine also writes, "He ha[s] chosen us, predestinating us to be such by His grace."¹⁷⁶ In other words, predestination effects the operation of God's grace, but at the same time predestination itself is operated by God's grace. Since only those who had been chosen or elected are called,¹⁷⁷ God's grace only operates on and within those God has chosen. In other words, not all humans are called, but only those elected are called. Although God's grace is irresistible, it only operates on and within whom God has chosen,¹⁷⁸ thus only a certain number of people are saved. This is the reason why God's grace is irresistible but not all men are saved.

Predestination is God's prevenient action, because it precedes men's merits – God chooses men before men does anything good. Since predestination is God's prevenient action, God's grace resulting from and operating in His predestination is also prevenient. Thus, regarding the scope of operation, it is appropriate to say that God's prevenient grace only operates on and within those God has chosen beforehand.

3.3.4 Conclusion

God's prevenient grace is operated by the Holy Spirit, in Jesus Christ, through the external means including the divine law, environment and baptism by the Church, and also through the internal means including man's ability, will and deed. It operates in all the steps of our salvation, from justification through sanctification to perfection. It is irresistible, thus when it operates on and within those God has chosen, they will surely be saved and perfected.

¹⁷⁴ Ibid., chap. 19, in p. 817.

¹⁷⁵ Ibid.

¹⁷⁶ Ibid., chap. 36, in p. 831.

¹⁷⁷ See *ibid.*, chap. 33, in p.828.

¹⁷⁸ See *ibid.*, chap. 19, in p. 817.

3.4 Conclusion

God's prevenient grace is God's gift that precedes men's merits. It is gratuitous – given freely by God to men according to His mercy, and sovereignly – given to men according to God's purpose. It is operated by the Holy Spirit in Jesus Christ through the external and internal means. It operates in all three steps of the process of human salvation – justification, sanctification and perfection. It only operates on and within those God has chosen. The chosen cannot reject God's calling, for God's grace is irresistible, thus His calling must be effectual. Prevenient grace is not only the nature of grace that exists at the initial step of salvation. Indeed, it exists and operates throughout the whole process of human salvation.

CHAPTER 4

WESLEY'S DOCTRINE OF GRACE: A BRIEF LITERATURE REVIEW

After having done a brief study on Augustine's concept of prevenient grace, we have to proceed to study Wesley's concept of prevenient grace. Before doing so, we also need a framework for this study. Same as Augustine, Wesley never wrote any book on systematic theology. Thus, he did not systematise his doctrine of grace into a systematic framework, although he did treat it systematically in his sermons. Hence, it is needful to have a review on the frameworks as provided by Outler, Collins and Maddox.

4.1 Albert C. Outler

In his introduction to Wesley's collection of sermons, Outler identifies God's grace as the important theme that runs throughout Wesley's soteriology. Firstly, Outler concludes, "The heart of Wesley was always its lively sense of God's grace at work at every level of creation and history in persons and communities."¹⁷⁹ Further, Outler outlines four parallel and counterbalanced essences of Wesley's doctrine of grace. The first is his "Protestant principle" "that God alone is God, with no rivals in creation."¹⁸⁰ The second is his "Greek Christian heritage" "that the Holy Spirit [is] the mediator of all graces – sufficient grace in all, irresistible in none."¹⁸¹ The third is Wesley ecclesiological "conviction that all the means of grace are the Spirit's gifts to the priesthood of all believers and, under the Spirit's guidance, to a representative priesthood."¹⁸² The fourth is his catholic "theme of participation," which suggests that "all life is of grace and all grace is the mediation of Christ by the Holy Spirit."¹⁸³

From these four parallel and counterbalanced essences identified by Outler, it can be

¹⁷⁹ Albert C. Outler, Introduction to *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 1, *Sermons I: 1-33* (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1984), 98.

¹⁸⁰ Ibid.

¹⁸¹ Ibid.

¹⁸² Ibid., 98-9.

¹⁸³ Ibid., 99.

concluded that Outler developed his quadrilateral framework in studying Wesley's doctrine of grace. In this framework, he not only identifies the quadrilateral essences of Wesley's doctrine of grace, but also the source, the immanency and the operation of grace. First, there is no other source of grace but God, for "God alone is God, with no rivals in creation."¹⁸⁴ Second, God's grace is immanent, for it operates at "every level of creation and history in persons and communities."¹⁸⁵ Third, the Holy Spirit is the only agent that operates God's grace through Jesus Christ. Fourth, all the means of grace in the Church are the gifts of the Holy Spirit.

4.2 K. J. Collins

On the other hand, Collins studies Wesley's soteriology from three aspects: its dynamic, order and purpose.¹⁸⁶ The dynamic of Wesley's soteriology, as identified by Collins, is "a number of conjunctions" with "the principal one" "being that of law and grace."¹⁸⁷ The order of Wesley's soteriology, as according to Collins, is "parallelism with a difference," that is, the same term has similar and also different meaning in different contexts.¹⁸⁸ For example, grace in justification is the same and also distinct from grace in sanctification.¹⁸⁹ The purpose of Wesley's soteriology is holiness in this life (that is faith to God and love to our neighbour) and also fullness in eternity.¹⁹⁰ Collins concludes his study by pointing out the necessity to study Wesley's soteriology holistically, by considering the "tensions and conjunctions" in his soteriology.¹⁹¹

Collins' framework has successfully provided a holistic view on Wesley's soteriology. This holistic view has successfully pointed out the important dynamic that runs through Wesley's soteriology, which is the tension that exists in the conjunction of opposite concepts,

¹⁸⁴ Ibid., 98.

¹⁸⁵ Ibid.

¹⁸⁶ Kenneth J. Collins, *The Scripture Way of Salvation: The Heart of John Wesley's Theology* (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1997), 14.

¹⁸⁷ Ibid. The law here refers to moral law. See *ibid.*

¹⁸⁸ See *ibid.*, 15.

¹⁸⁹ Ibid.

¹⁹⁰ Ibid., 16.

¹⁹¹ Ibid., 16-7.

for example, grace and law. This dynamic enables Wesley, in building his soteriology, to bring opposite concepts from diverse sources into a harmonious order.

4.3 Randy L. Maddox

In studying Wesley's works, Maddox identifies Wesley's "orienting concern" in his works as something that "preserve[s] the vital tension between two truths that he viewed as co-definitive of Christianity: without God's grace, we *cannot* be saved; while without our (grace-empowered, but uncoerced) participation, God's grace *will not* save."¹⁹² Maddox defines this grace as "responsible grace."¹⁹³ In other words, "responsible grace" is the dynamic of Wesley's works.

With this "orienting concern", Maddox develops a systematic framework to organize Wesley's theology. Systematic here is not "in the Hegelian sense of being derived from or subsumable under a single idea or structure."¹⁹⁴ Indeed, it means a "Christian experience of salvation as the recovery of holiness."¹⁹⁵ In other words, Maddox develops a framework that uses "responsible grace" as the theme in reflecting Wesley's soteriology. Maddox justifies his approach by asserting that his framework is "appropriate to Wesley's therapeutic soteriology" and "preserves the creation/re-creation parameters that distinguish his theology from much of the later Wesleyan traditions."¹⁹⁶ Then in this framework, Maddox discusses Wesley's soteriology from eight aspects: Wesley's epistemology, doctrine of God, anthropology, Christology, pneumatology, process of salvation, means of grace and eschatology.¹⁹⁷

From his work, Maddox has successfully identified the tension in Wesley's soteriology, that is, the grace of God and the participation of men. With this tension as the theme, Maddox has successfully systematised Wesley's soteriology into eight aspects, proving that although

¹⁹² Randy L. Maddox, *Responsible Grace: John Wesley's Practical Theology* (Nashville: Kingswood Boks, 1994), 19.

¹⁹³ Ibid.

¹⁹⁴ Ibid., 25.

¹⁹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁹⁷ Ibid.

Wesley does not write a book on systematic theology, he has “touched on every major area of Christian doctrine at one time or other in his pastoral career.”¹⁹⁸

4.4 Comments

These three scholars study Wesley’s doctrine of grace and soteriology from different approaches. Outler’s concern is on the diverse sources Wesley used in his doctrine of grace, Collins’ concern is on the holistic study on Wesley’s works, while Maddox’s concern is on systematising Wesley’s soteriology. The three of them have been successful in their approaches, developing their own frameworks in studying Wesley’s doctrine of grace and soteriology, presenting to us the richness and system of Wesley’s doctrine of grace and soteriology.

Among these three scholars, Maddox agrees with Outler that grace is the prominent theme in that runs through Wesley’s work on soteriology. However, Collins disagrees with Outler, suggesting that the main dynamic of Wesley’s soteriology is the tension between grace and moral law. Collins argues that Outler’s overemphasis on one side of the tension (grace) has led to his neglect on the other side of the tension (moral law).

Although these three scholars have different approaches and emphases in studying Wesley’s doctrine of grace and soteriology, there are two similarities. First, they agree that Wesley used various sources in his works. Second, they agree that Wesley built his soteriology on the tensions between different concepts, but they have different opinions on what these tensions are. Outler and Maddox agree that this tension is the grace of God and the participation of men, while Collins argues that the proper tension is grace and moral law. Superficially, Collins disagrees with Outler and Maddox, but in fact they agree with each other. They are discussing the same concept of Wesley in different terms. Collins’s “moral law” in fact has same concept as Outler and Maddox’s “participation of men,” because the “moral law”

¹⁹⁸ Ibid., 15.

requires men's obedience, thus it is also "participation of men." Hence, the tension between the grace of God and the participation of men is the "dynamic" or "orienting concern" of Wesley's soteriology and doctrine of grace.

Among these three frameworks, which one is suitable for the study of this thesis on Wesley's concept of prevenient grace? To the author of this thesis, the most suitable framework should be the same framework used to study Augustine's concept of prevenient grace, which consists of three components – definition, nature and operation. This definition-nature-operation framework is appropriate because of three reasons. First, using the same framework will ease the task to compare Augustine's and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace. Second, Wesley's concept of prevenient grace may be organised into the three components of this framework. Last and the most importantly, this framework will not neglect the essence of Wesley's soteriology and the doctrine of grace, that is, the tension between the grace of God and the participation of men. In fact, by discussing the nature of prevenient grace from the aspect of God and men, as well as the operation of God's grace on and within men, the tension between grace of God and participation of men will be discussed also.

4.5 Conclusion

In this chapter we have reviewed three frameworks proposed by three Wesleyan scholars in their studies of Wesley's doctrine of grace and soteriology. We have seen that the essence of Wesley's soteriology and doctrine of grace is the tension between the grace of God and the participation of men. We have also seen that the definition-nature-operation framework is appropriate also for the study on Wesley's concept of prevenient grace. The following chapter will study Wesley's concept of prevenient grace with this framework.

CHAPTER 5

WESLEY'S CONCEPT OF PREVENIENT GRACE: A BRIEF STUDY

After reviewing scholars' studies on Wesley doctrine of grace and soteriology in the previous chapter, this chapter will make a brief study on Wesley's concept of prevenient grace from three aspects – definition, nature and operation of prevenient grace.

5.1 Definition of Prevenient Grace

What is prevenient grace in Wesley's doctrine of grace? Before defining prevenient grace, it is good for us to know what Wesley meant by 'the grace of God.' Wesley defines God's grace as assistance of God.¹⁹⁹ To Wesley, God's grace is "excellent knowledge of Jesus Christ our Lord," "free love ... unmerited mercy"²⁰⁰ and "the mere mercy of God through the merits of his well-beloved Son."²⁰¹ God's grace is "the power of God in Christ"²⁰² and also the "power of the Holy Ghost, reigning in his heart."²⁰³ Thus, it is obvious that for Wesley, God's grace is God's assistance in the form of knowledge, love and mercy, but most importantly the power in Jesus Christ operated by the Holy Spirit in our hearts.

Wesley writes,

If we take this in its utmost extent it [salvation] will include all that is wrought in the soul by what is frequently termed 'natural conscience', but more properly, 'preventing grace'; all the 'drawings' of 'the Father', the desires after God, which, if we yield to them, increase more and more; all that 'light' wherewith the Son of God 'enlightened everyone

¹⁹⁹ John Wesley, "Sermon 116: What is Man?" in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 4, *Sermons IV: 115-151*, by John Wesley (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1987), §11, p. 24.

²⁰⁰ John Wesley, "Sermon 12: The Witness of Our Own Spirit," in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 1, *Sermons I: 1-33*, by John Wesley (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1984), §15, in p. 309.

²⁰¹ John Wesley, "Sermon 16: The Means of Grace," in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 1, *Sermons I: 1-33*, by John Wesley, II.6, p. 383.

²⁰² John Wesley, "Sermon 14: The Repentance of Believers," in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 1, *Sermons I: 1-33*, by John Wesley, II.6, p. 349.

²⁰³ John Wesley, "Sermon 9: The Spirit of Bondage and of Adoption," in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 1, *Sermons I: 1-33*, by John Wesley, III.1, p. 260; See also Wesley, "Sermon 12: The Witness of Our Own Spirit," §15, p. 309; Wesley, "Sermon 51: The Good Steward," in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 1, *Sermons I: 1-33*, by John Wesley, I.8, p. 286; Wesley, "Sermon 16: The Means of Grace," II.6, p. 383.

that cometh into the world’, *showing* every man ‘to do justly, to love mercy, and to walk humbly with his God’; all the *convictions* which his Spirit from time to time works in every child of man. Although it is true the generality of men stifle them as soon as possible, and after a while forget, or at least deny, that ever they had them at all.²⁰⁴

This passage is probably a good summary of Wesley’s concept on prevenient grace. Several of Wesley’s teachings on prevenient grace can be drawn out from this passage to constitute his definition of prevenient grace. First, the term Wesley uses for prevenient grace is “preventing grace”. Second, to Wesley, prevenient grace is the same as “natural conscience.” Third, prevenient grace is the work of triune God – it is “all the ‘drawings’ of ‘the Father’”, all the light of the Son, and “all the *convictions*” of the Holy Spirit. Fourth, the results of prevenient grace (the work of the triune God) are, men are drawn by the Father to desire God, enlightened by the Son to do justice and mercy and to walk humbly with God, and convicted by the Holy Spirit of their sins. Fifth, the prevenient grace of God is given to every person, as Wesley writes, “[to enlighten] everyone that cometh into the world” and “from time to time works in every child of man.”

Hence, to Wesley, prevenient grace is God’s assistance given to us in the form of His power in Jesus Christ, operated by the Holy Spirit in everyone’s heart in the form of his natural conscience. It is the work of the triune God – God the Father draws us to God, God the Son enlightens us to work with God, and God the Holy Spirit convicts us of our sins.

5.2 Nature of Prevenient Grace

Prevenient grace is God’s power in Christ given to men through the operation of the Holy Spirit in their hearts in the form of their natural consciences in order to assist them. As pointed out by Wesleyan scholars, Outler and Maddox as well as Collins (though in different terms), the essence, dynamic or orienting concept of Wesley’s soteriology and doctrine of grace is the tension between the grace of God and the participation of men. Thus, it is

²⁰⁴ John Wesley, “Sermon 43: The Scripture Way of Salvation,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley, I.2, in p. 156-7.

appropriate to study the nature of prevenient grace from the aspects of God the Giver and men the receivers, since this will preserve the tension between the grace of God and the participation of men.

5.2.1 The Giver – God

What are the natures of God’s grace from the aspect of the Giver? Although Wesley did not write much on the natures of God’s grace directly, three principles on the natures of God’s grace can be drawn out from his explanation on grace.

First, Wesley uses different terms in describing God’s grace, among them are of “preventing” grace, “justifying” grace, “sanctifying” grace,²⁰⁵ “convincing grace”²⁰⁶ and “saving grace.”²⁰⁷ Wesley does not mean that these are different graces of God, for he writes “[God’s] free, almighty grace, first preventing us, and then accompanying us every moment.”²⁰⁸ It is obvious that what Wesley meant is that it is the same grace of God that prevents us at the very beginning of our salvation and accompanies us throughout the process of our salvation. Wesley uses different terms in order to describe the same grace of God that operates in the different stages in the process of salvation. “Saving grace” refers to God’s grace itself. In other words, God’s grace is “saving grace,” because “grace is the source ... of salvation.”²⁰⁹ It is God’s grace that saves us from sins, so God’s grace itself is “saving grace”. God’s grace, or saving grace, works in different stages in the process of our salvation. It works before our repentance and justification, “before we are ‘accepted in the Beloved’,”²¹⁰ to begin to deliver us from “a blind, unfeeling heart,”²¹¹ so it is called prevenient grace. God’s grace

²⁰⁵ Wesley, “Sermon 16: The Means of Grace,” II.1, in p. 381.

²⁰⁶ John Wesley, “Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Own Salvation,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 3, *Sermons III: 71-114*, by John Wesley, II.1, p. 204.

²⁰⁷ John Wesley, “Sermon 104: On Attending the Church Service,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 3, *Sermons III: 71-114*, by John Wesley, §§28, 30, in p. 476.

²⁰⁸ Wesley, “Sermon 43: The Scripture Way of Salvation,” III.8, in p. 166.

²⁰⁹ John Wesley, “Sermon 1: Salvation by Faith,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 1, *Sermons I: 1-33*, by John Wesley, §3, p. 118.

²¹⁰ John Wesley, “Sermon 11: The Witness of the Spirit, II,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 1, *Sermons I: 1-33*, by John Wesley, V.4, p. 298.

²¹¹ Wesley, “Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Own Salvation,” II.1, in p. 204.

works in our repentance, convinces us to repent of our sins, farther delivers us from “the heart of stone,” and leads us to “experience the proper Christian salvation,” which consists of “justification and sanctification,”²¹² so it is called convincing grace. God’s grace works in our justification, by which “we are saved from the guilt of sin, and restored to the favour of God,”²¹³ so it is called justifying grace. God’s grace works in our sanctification, by which “we are saved from the power and root of sin, and restored to the image of God”²¹⁴ in us, so it is also called sanctifying grace. It is obvious now that prevenient grace, convincing grace, justifying grace and sanctifying grace refer to the same grace of God – the saving grace – that works in different stages in the process of our salvation.

To conclude, God’s grace is the saving grace that works as prevenient, convincing, justifying and sanctifying grace, in order to convince us to repent of our sins, so that we will be justified and able to enter into process of sanctification. Prevenient grace is the same as convincing, justifying and sanctifying grace in the sense that they are all God’s grace, it is however also distinct from convincing, justifying and sanctifying grace in their operations in the different stages in process of our salvation.²¹⁵ Thus, prevenient grace are in some respects the same as convincing, justifying and sanctifying grace, and also some characteristics that are distinct from them.

Second, prevenient grace is God’s power in Jesus Christ conveyed by the Holy Spirit to men. God the Father is the author, God the Son is the mediator, and God the Holy Spirit is the agent to operate God’s grace. Wesley writes, prevenient grace is “all the ‘drawings’ of ‘the Father’”²¹⁶ and “the gift of God.”²¹⁷ God’s grace is God’s power in Christ,²¹⁸ given to men

²¹² Ibid.

²¹³ Ibid.

²¹⁴ Ibid.

²¹⁵ This is another example for Collins’ “parallelism with a difference.” Kenneth J. Collins, *The Scripture Way of Salvation: The Heart of John Wesley’s Theology*, 15.

²¹⁶ Wesley, “Sermon 43: The Scripture Way of Salvation,” I.2, in p.156.

²¹⁷ Wesley, “Sermon 1: Salvation by Faith,” III.3, in p. 126. See also John Wesley, “Sermon 105: On Conscience,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 4, *Sermons IV: 115-151*, by John Wesley, I.5, in p. 482.

²¹⁸ Wesley, “Sermon 14: The Repentance of Believers,” II.6, in p. 349.

through Jesus Christ. This statement is supported by Ephesians 2:8 “[God] might show the exceeding riches of his grace in his kindness toward us through Christ”²¹⁹ and 1 Corinthians 1:4 “The grace of God, through Jesus Christ thy Lord.”²²⁰ How does God’s grace relate to men? The Holy Spirit is the agent that operates God’s saving grace – prevenient, convincing, justifying and sanctifying – in our hearts.²²¹ Prevenient grace is God’s grace, thus it is also God’s power in Jesus Christ operated by the Holy Spirit.

Third, prevenient grace is “free in all, and free for all.”²²² “Free in all” means it is totally free; “free for all” means it was given to everyone. God’s grace is free in all, given to men on the according to “[God’s] free, undeserved favour, favour altogether underserved,”²²³ on the ground of “the merits of Christ.”²²⁴ It is also free for all, as written by Wesley, “preventing grace of God ... is common to all.”²²⁵ Prevenient grace is given to “everyone that cometh into the world,” that is, “every child of man.”²²⁶ “Every man has a greater or less measure of this [(preventing grace)].”²²⁷ Thus, prevenient grace is free in all and free for all.

To conclude, prevenient grace is not another grace of God, but it is God’s grace that operates before repentance and justification. It is God’s power in Christ operated by the Holy Spirit. It is free in all and free for all.

5.2.2 The Receivers – Men

We have seen the natures of prevenient grace from the aspect of the Giver. Then, what are the natures of prevenient grace in relation to men, the receivers of prevenient grace?

²¹⁹ Wesley, “Sermon 1: Salvation by Faith,” III.3, in p. 126.

²²⁰ John Wesley, “Sermon 9: The Spirit of Bondage and of Adoption,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 1, *Sermons I: 1-33*, by John Wesley, II.10, in p. 260.

²²¹ Wesley, “Sermon 12: The Witness of Our Own Spirit,” §15, p. 309.

²²² John Wesley, “Sermon 110: Free Grace,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 3, *Sermons III: 71-114*, by John Wesley, §2, in p. 544.

²²³ Wesley, “Sermon 1: Salvation by Faith,” III.3, in p. 126.

²²⁴ Wesley, “Sermon 12: The Witness of Our Own Spirit,” §15, in p. 309.

²²⁵ John Wesley, “The Principles of a Methodist,” in Rupert E. Davies, ed. *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 9, *The Methodist Societies: History, Nature, and Design*, by John Wesley (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1989), §29, in p. 64, quoting Mr. Tucker.

²²⁶ Wesley, “Sermon 43: The Scripture Way of Salvation,” I.2, in p. 157.

²²⁷ Wesley, “Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Own Salvation,” III.4, in p. 207.

First, prevenient grace is necessary for men. Prevenient grace is necessary for the creation of man in God's image. Wesley writes, "It was free grace that formed man of the dust of the ground, and breathed into him a living soul, and stamped on the soul the image of God, and 'put all things under his feet'."²²⁸ Prevenient grace is necessary for our daily living. Wesley writes, "The same free grace continues to us, at this day, life, and breath, and all things."²²⁹ Prevenient grace is necessary for our salvation, for "salvation begins with what is usually termed (and very properly) 'preventing grace'."²³⁰ Wesley points out that prevenient grace is necessary from the beginning of our life, to our daily lives, and the beginning of our salvation.

Second, since God's grace is free in all, men cannot earn God's grace with their own merits. Wesley writes, "[God's grace is] free in all, that is, no way depending on any power or merit in man."²³¹ Thus, men have "no claim to the feast of [God's] mercies," "for there is nothing we are, or have, or do, which can deserve the least thing at God's hand."²³² This is because we are all sinners,²³³ our natures "inclined to evil,"²³⁴ thus "all our works, all our righteousness, which were before our believing, merited nothing of God but condemnation."²³⁵ Hence, prevenient grace is purely a free gift of God, something that men cannot have any merits to earn it.

Third, prevenient grace is free for all, thus it is given to every man in the form of "natural conscience."²³⁶ Wesley writes, "Conscience is 'a supernatural gift of God,'"²³⁷ and "no man living is entirely destitute of what is vulgarly called 'natural conscience'."²³⁸ Every man has natural conscience, thus every man is given prevenient grace.

²²⁸ Wesley, "Sermon 1: Salvation by Faith," §1, in p. 117-8.

²²⁹ Ibid., §1, p. 118.

²³⁰ Wesley, "Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Own Salvation," II.1, in p. 203.

²³¹ Wesley, "Sermon 110: Free Grace," §3, in p. 545.

²³² Wesley, "Sermon 1: Salvation by Faith," §1, in p. 118.

²³³ See John Wesley, "The Principles of a Methodist," in Rupert E. Davies, ed. *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 9, *The Methodist Societies: History, Nature, and Design*, by John Wesley, §3, in p. 51.

²³⁴ Ibid.

²³⁵ Ibid., III.3, in p. 126.

²³⁶ Wesley, "Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Own Salvation," III.4, in p. 307.

²³⁷ Wesley, "Sermon 105: On Conscience," I.5, in p. 482.

²³⁸ Wesley, "Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Own Salvation," III.4, in p. 307.

To conclude, prevenient grace is necessary for men's living and salvation. It is free in all, something that men in no way can earn it. It is free for all. Even though men cannot earn it, it is given freely by God to every man.

5.2.3 Conclusion

In conclusion, prevenient grace is God's grace that operates before repentance and justification. It is God's power in Christ operated by the Holy Spirit in the form of natural conscience in every one's heart. It is free in all, and free for all, that is, given freely to everyone, on the ground of Christ's merit.

Prevenient grace is necessary for our being, living and salvation. We cannot exist and live without it. Since we are all sinners, all our thoughts and deeds, no matter how righteous they are, only deserve condemnation. Thus, we need God's grace, but at the same time we do not deserve it and cannot earn it. On the other hand, God's grace is free in all; it cannot be earned. It is free for all, and even though we cannot earn it, it is given to every one of us.

5.3 Operation of Prevenient Grace

What is the operation of prevenient grace? As mentioned in section 5.2.1., the operation of prevenient grace is the operation of the Holy Spirit. In this part, the operation of prevenient grace will be examined from three aspects – means, effects and scope of the operation.

5.3.1 Means of Operation

Prevenient grace is God's power in Christ operated by the Holy Spirit in our hearts. However, how does it operate in our hearts? It operates internally in our hearts and externally upon our hearts.

5.3.1.1 Internal Means of Operation

What are the internal means of the operation of prevenient grace? First, prevenient grace operates as our natural conscience. For Wesley, our natural conscience is same as God's prevenient grace.²³⁹ In other words, God's prevenient grace operates as our natural conscience. "Conscience," Wesley explains, "is that faculty whereby we are at once conscious of our own thoughts, words, and actions, and of their merit or demerit, of their being good or bad, and consequently deserving either praise or censure."²⁴⁰ Wesley continues to point out that conscience has "a threefold office."²⁴¹ Wesley writes:

First, [conscience] is a *witness*, testifying what we have done, in thought, or word, or action. Secondly, it is a *judge*, passing sentence on what we have done, that it is good or evil. And thirdly, it in some sort *executes* the sentence, by occasioning a degree of complacency in him that does well, and a degree of uneasiness in him that does evil.²⁴²

In other words, conscience is our ability to discern good and evil. With our conscience, we are not only aware of what we think, speak and do, to discern whether they are good or evil, but also to have good feelings on good thoughts, words and actions, and bad feelings on evil thoughts, words and actions. This ability is usually known as "natural conscience,"²⁴³ for "it is found in all men,"²⁴⁴ "not only in Christians, but in all Mahometans, all pagans, yea the vilest of savages;"²⁴⁵ but "it is more properly termed 'preventing grace',"²⁴⁶ for it is "a supernatural gift of God, above all [God's] natural endowments."²⁴⁷ In other words, natural conscience is our ability to discern good and evil; this ability, found in everyman, is given by God

²³⁹ Wesley, "Sermon 43: The Scripture Way of Salvation," I.2, in p. 157; Wesley, "Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Own Salvation," III.4, in p. 207.

²⁴⁰ Wesley, "Sermon 105: On Conscience," I.3, in p. 481.

²⁴¹ *Ibid.*, I.7, in p. 483.

²⁴² *Ibid.*

²⁴³ Wesley, "Sermon 43: The Scripture Way of Salvation," I.2, in p.157; Wesley, "Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Own Salvation," III.4, in p. 207; Wesley, "Sermon 105: On Conscience," I.5, in p. 482.

²⁴⁴ *Ibid.*

²⁴⁵ John Wesley, "Sermon 129: Heavenly Treasure in Earthen Vessels," in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 4, *Sermons IV: 115-151*, by John Wesley, I. 1, p. 163.

²⁴⁶ Wesley, "Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Own Salvation," III.4, in p. 207; See also Wesley, "Sermon 43: The Scripture Way of Salvation," I.2, in p.157.

²⁴⁷ Wesley, "Sermon 105: On Conscience," I.5, in p. 482.

preveniently, that is, before we are saved. Thus, prevenient grace operates in every man as natural conscience.

Second, prevenient grace operates through our “understanding,” “affections,” and “liberty.”²⁴⁸ Wesley writes,

[God] did not take away your understanding, but enlightened and strengthened it. He did not destroy any of your affections; rather they were more vigorous than before. Least of all did he take away your liberty, your power of choosing good or evil; he did not *force* you; but being *assisted* by his grace you, like Mary, *chose* the better part.²⁴⁹

In fact, “understanding,” “affections” and “liberty” are God’s prevenient gifts to every man. God’s grace operates preveniently through our “understanding,” “affections” and “liberty,” to enable and assist us, but not to force us, to choose good. In other words, we have the ability to choose good, repent and believe because of the operation of prevenient grace in our faculties of “understanding,” “affections” and “liberty.”

Prevenient grace operates in every one’s heart as “natural conscience.” It also operates through our faculties of “understanding,” “affections” and “liberty.”

5.3.1.2 External Means of Operation

What are the external means of the operation of prevenient grace? First, prevenient grace operates through “some awful providence” and “[God’s] Word,” “touches the heart of him that lay asleep in darkness and in the shadow of death.”²⁵⁰ Wesley regards the person who is “asleep in darkness and in the shadow of death” as “natural man.”²⁵¹ “Natural man” is in “natural state,” a state where he is full of evil thoughts all the time,²⁵² spiritually indifferent,²⁵³

²⁴⁸ John Wesley, “Sermon 63: The General Spread of the Gospel,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley, §11.

²⁴⁹ *Ibid.*

²⁵⁰ Wesley, “Sermon 9: The Spirit of Bondage and of Adoption,” II.1, in p. 255.

²⁵¹ *Ibid.*, I.1, in p. 251.

²⁵² See John Wesley, “Sermon 41: Wandering Thoughts,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley, I.2, in p. 127; John Wesley, “Sermon 44: Original Sin,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley, II.1, III.1, in pp. 176, 183.

²⁵³ John Wesley, “Sermon 45: The New Birth,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley, II.4, in p. 192.

“discern[ing] neither spiritual good nor evil,” and “is utterly ignorant of God.”²⁵⁴ In other words, “natural man” refers to him who is not aware of his thoughts, words and actions, not able to discern spiritual good and evil, and neither feels good on his good thoughts, words and actions, nor feels bad on his evil thoughts, words and actions. Put simply, “natural man” refers to him who has no “natural conscience.” However, when prevenient grace operates through “some awful providence” and “[God’s] Word,”²⁵⁵ “natural man” is “terribly shaken out of his sleep, and wakes into a consciousness of his danger.”²⁵⁶ For the first time he is able to “discern the real state he is in.”²⁵⁷ “The inward, spiritual meaning of the law of God now begins to glare upon him.”²⁵⁸ “Now he truly desires to break loose from sin, and begins to struggle with it.”²⁵⁹ Now, because of the operation of prevenient grace, “natural man” is changed into man “‘under the law,’” under the “‘spirit of fear and bondage.’”²⁶⁰ This operation of prevenient grace in fact is in the form of man’s “natural conscience,” for it has the same effects as the effects of “natural conscience.” Wesley points out that, since prevenient grace operates in every man’s heart, causing every man to have “natural conscience,” “there is no man that is in a state of mere nature.”²⁶¹ In other words, there is no “natural man,” all men are at least “under the law,” for prevenient grace operates in every one’s heart as his natural conscience. The difference is only on the degree of its effects, that is, some have “greater” others have “less measure” of natural conscience.²⁶²

Second, regarding means of grace, Wesley writes, “By ‘means of grace’ I understand outward signs, words, or actions ordained of God, and appointed for this end – to be the *ordinary* channels whereby he might convey to men preventing, justifying, or sanctifying

²⁵⁴ Wesley, “Sermon 9: The Spirit of Bondage and of Adoption,” II.1, in p. 255.

²⁵⁵ Ibid.

²⁵⁶ Ibid.

²⁵⁷ Ibid.

²⁵⁸ Ibid., II.2, in p. 255.

²⁵⁹ Ibid., II.7, in p. 258.

²⁶⁰ Ibid., II.9, in p. 258.

²⁶¹ Wesley, “Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Own Salvation,” III.4, in p. 207.

²⁶² Ibid.

grace.”²⁶³ What are those means of grace? In his sermon on “The Means of Grace,” Wesley points out three means of grace – “prayer,” “‘searching the Scriptures’,” and “partaking of the Lord’s Supper.”²⁶⁴ Wesley reminds us that the means of grace is mere channels God designed for us to attain His saving grace,²⁶⁵ “if separate[d] from the Spirit of God, [we] cannot profit at all, [or] conduce in any degree either to the knowledge or love of God.”²⁶⁶ Wesley further reminds us that in means of grace, “there is no *power* to save but in the Spirit of God, no *merit* but in the blood of Christ.”²⁶⁷ In other words, the means of grace is mere channels, which does not have power to save in itself.

Regarding the order God uses means of grace to bring a sinner to salvation, Wesley points out that first a “senseless wretch” is awakened by a “sermon,” a “conversation,” “some awful providence,” or “an immediate stroke of his [(God’s)] convincing Spirit, without any outward means at all.”²⁶⁸ Then, this awakened man, who desires “to flee from the wrath to come,” “purposely goes to *hear* how it may be done.”²⁶⁹ After hearing from “a preacher who speaks to the heart, he is amazed, and begins ‘searching the Scriptures’, whether these things are so.”²⁷⁰ “The more he *hears* and *reads*, the more convinced he is; and the more he *meditates* thereon day and night.”²⁷¹ “He begins also to *talk* of the things of God . . . and to talk with God, to *pray* to him.”²⁷² He also begins to pray with “those who know God.”²⁷³ Then, after struggling between Christ’s command on observance of the Lord’s Supper and his unworthiness as a sinner, he finally “breaks through” and begins to partake the Lord’s Supper.²⁷⁴ “And thus he continues in God’s way – in hearing, reading, meditating, praying, and partaking of the Lord’s Supper – till God . . . speaks to his heart, ‘Thy faith hath saved thee;

²⁶³ Wesley, “Sermon 16: The Means of Grace,” II.1, in p.381.

²⁶⁴ See *ibid.*, III.1-12, in pp. 384-90.

²⁶⁵ *Ibid.*, II.7, in p. 383.

²⁶⁶ *Ibid.*, II.3, in p. 382.

²⁶⁷ *Ibid.*, V.4, in p. 396.

²⁶⁸ *Ibid.*, V.1, in p. 393-4.

²⁶⁹ *Ibid.*, V.1, in p. 394.

²⁷⁰ *Ibid.*

²⁷¹ *Ibid.*

²⁷² *Ibid.*

²⁷³ *Ibid.*

²⁷⁴ *Ibid.*

go in peace.”²⁷⁵

It is obvious that, according to Wesley, the order of means of grace is searching the Scripture, then prayer, and then partaking of the Lord’s Supper. It seems that Wesley teaches us that we are saved by observing these means of grace. In fact, this is not true. As pointed out by Wesley, salvation is only in the Holy Spirit through the blood of Christ,²⁷⁶ thus these means of grace cannot save us. It is by using these means of grace that we wait upon God’s salvation. These means of grace – searching the Scriptures, prayer, and partaking of the Lord’s Supper – as pointed by Wesley, are “the *ordinary* channels whereby he [(God)] might convey to men preventing, justifying, or sanctifying grace.”²⁷⁷

Since the means of grace are channels for prevenient grace, does it mean that Wesley allows unbelievers to partake the Lord’s Supper? Although this question is debated vigorously by scholars,²⁷⁸ it is obvious from Wesley’s sermon on “The Means of Grace” and journal, it is obvious that he does allow, at least theoretically, unbelievers to partake the Lord’s Supper. In “The Means of Grace” V.1, Wesley writes that a sinner “continues in God’s way – in hearing, reading, meditating, praying, and partaking of the Lord’s Supper – till God ... speaks to his heart, ‘Thy faith hath saved thee; go in peace.’”²⁷⁹ In his journal (31 December 1739) he writes,

Therefore I believe it right for him who knows he has not faith (i.e., that conquering faith),
 To go to church;
 To communicate; [(that is, to partake the Lord’s Supper)]
 To fast;
 To use as much private prayer as he can, and
 To read the Scripture;

²⁷⁵ Ibid.

²⁷⁶ Ibid., V.4, in p. 396.

²⁷⁷ Ibid., II.1, in p.381.

²⁷⁸ Maddox, *Responsible Grace: John Wesley’s Practical Theology*, 228.

²⁷⁹ Ibid., V.1, in p. 394.

(Because I believe these are ‘means of grace’, i.e., do ordinarily convey God’s grace to unbelievers.)²⁸⁰

In these two writings Wesley makes himself clear that he allows unbelievers to partake the Lord’s Supper. He explains it from three aspects. First is the historical aspect. The early Church affirmed that the Lord’s Supper was a “converting ordinance,” but in latter times the Church asserted that the Lord’s Supper was not a “converting, but a confirming ordinance.”²⁸¹ Second, Wesley points out from our experience “the very beginning of your salvation (perhaps, in some, the first deep conviction) was wrought at the Lord’s Supper.”²⁸² Finally, from the biblical aspect, the Lord’s Supper is a “converting ordinance,” for Christ had commanded “those very men who were then *unconverted*, who had *not* yet ‘received the Holy Ghost’, who (in the full sense of the word) were not *believers*, to ‘do this in remembrance of him’.”²⁸³ Thus, according to Wesley, from the aspects of history, experience and the Scriptures, it is proven that the Lord’s Supper is a converting ordinance that can convey prevenient grace to the unbelievers.

Therefore, according to Wesley, the means of grace, including the Lord’s Supper, are channels designed by God to convey His grace – prevenient, convincing, justifying and sanctifying grace. The means of grace include, but are not limited to, attending church, hearing and reading the word of God, praying, “‘partaking the Lord’s Supper’,” and all other “ordinance of God,” (as written by Wesley, “all the ordinance of God are the stated channels of his grace to man.”)²⁸⁴

To conclude, prevenient grace operates through God’s providence, God’s Word and the means of grace designed by God.

²⁸⁰ John Wesley, “Journal 4,” in W. Reginald Ward and Richard P. Heitzenrater, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 19, *Journal and Diaries II (1738-1743)*, by John Wesley (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1990), 31 December 1739, in p. 133.

²⁸¹ *Ibid.*, 27 June 1740, in p. 158.

²⁸² *Ibid.*

²⁸³ *Ibid.*, 27 June 1740, in p. 158.

²⁸⁴ John Wesley, “A Second Letter to the Author of the Enthusiasm of Methodist, etc.,” in Gerald R. Cragg, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 11, *The Appeals to Men of Reason and Religion and Certain Related Open Letters*, by John Wesley, §39, in p. 418.

5.3.1.3 Conclusion

In conclusion, prevenient grace is operated by the Holy Spirit internally in us and externally upon us. Internally, prevenient grace operates as our “natural conscience,” and also operates through our faculties of “understanding,” “affections,” and “liberty.” Externally, prevenient grace operates through God’s providence and means of grace.

5.3.2 Effects and Scope of Operation

What are the effects of the operation of prevenient grace to us? In discussing the means of the operation of prevenient grace, its effects and scope have also been discussed. Thus, further discussion is probably not needed. This chapter will attempt to give a summary on the effects and scope of the operation of prevenient grace.

Through God’s providence or His words, prevenient grace changes a “natural man” into a man “under the law” by giving him “natural conscience.” This man, who previously in his “natural state,” being ignorant and indifferent to God and his own sins,²⁸⁵ now with “natural conscience,” is aware of his doings (in thoughts, words and actions), able to discern good and evil, and feel bad about sin.²⁸⁶ By the operation of prevenient grace in the form of “natural conscience,” his desire is drawn to the Father, his “understanding” is enlightened by the Son and he is convicted by the Spirit of his own sins.²⁸⁷ Prevenient grace also operates through his “affections,”²⁸⁸ causing him to have “a degree of long-suffering, of gentleness, of fidelity, meekness, temperance.”²⁸⁹ Consequently, he has “the first wish to please God, the first dawn of light concerning his will, and the first slight, transient conviction of having sinned against [God].”²⁹⁰ By further assistance of prevenient grace on the faculty of his “liberty,” he is

²⁸⁵ See Wesley, “Sermon 9: The Spirit of Bondage and of Adoption,” II.1, in p. 251.

²⁸⁶ Wesley, “Sermon 105: On Conscience,” I.3, in p. 483.

²⁸⁷ See Wesley, “Sermon 43: The Scripture Way of Salvation,” I.2, in p. 156-7; see also Wesley, “Sermon 63: The General Spread of the Gospel,” §11.

²⁸⁸ See *ibid.*

²⁸⁹ Wesley, “Sermon 11: The Witness of the Spirit, II,” V.4, in p. 298.

²⁹⁰ Wesley, “Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Own Salvation,” II.1, in p. 203.

now able to avoid evil²⁹¹ and choose good.²⁹² He is drawn to use the means of grace – attending church, “searching the Scriptures,” “prayer,” and even “partaking the Lord’s Supper” – to wait upon God’s salvation. Then to those who are “‘poor in spirit’,” that is, those who are “humble,” “who know themselves,” and “who are convinced of sin,” God gives them the “first repentance which is previous to faith in Christ.”²⁹³ Finally, he is brought to Christ²⁹⁴ through means of grace. Wesley quoted Mr. Tucker, “For the preventing grace of God, which is common to all, is sufficient to *bring* us to Christ, though it is not sufficient to carry us any *further* till we are justified.”²⁹⁵ In conclusion, the ultimate effect of the operation of prevenient grace is “to *bring* us to Christ” so that we will be justified by justifying grace.²⁹⁶

Is the operation of prevenient grace irresistible? Concerning the irresistibility of God’s grace, Wesley writes, “the grace which brings faith, and thereby salvation into the soul, is irresistible *at that moment*.”²⁹⁷ He asserts that “most believers do at some other times find God *irresistibly* acting upon their souls.”²⁹⁸ He agrees that “in those eminently styled ‘the elect’ (if such there be) the grace of God is so far *irresistible* that they cannot but believe and be finally saved.”²⁹⁹ On the other hand, Wesley also asserts that “in general, [God’s grace] does not act *irresistib[ly]*, but we *may* comply therewith or *may not*.”³⁰⁰ He claims that God’s grace is not

²⁹¹ Ibid.

²⁹² Wesley, “Sermon 63: The General Spread of the Gospel,” §11. Although in his “Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Own Salvation,” (II.1, in p. 204) Wesley treated repentance as effect of “convincing grace,” but here he treated “first repentance” as effect of prevenient grace. It seems like Wesley is self-contradictory. Wesley is not self-contradictory, for he may mean that the first repentance is the effect of both prevenient and “convincing grace.” Prevenient grace convicts men of their sins, then together with “convincing grace” they both cause man to repent for the first time.

²⁹³ John Wesley, “Sermon 21: Sermon on the Mount, I,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 1, *Sermons I: 1-33*, by John Wesley, I.4, p. 477.

²⁹⁴ Wesley, “The Principles of a Methodist,” §29, in p. 64, quoting Mr. Tucker.

²⁹⁵ Ibid.

²⁹⁶ From the operation and effects of prevenient grace, it seems like there is some overlapping between prevenient and “convincing grace.” In other words, although Wesley did make a distinction between “preventing grace” and “convincing grace” (see V.2.1, par. 2), he did not always do that. Sometimes (or most of the time?) in discussing the operation of God’s grace in our salvation, he bypassed “convincing grace” by putting some of the works and effects of “convincing grace” into prevenient grace and others into “justifying grace.”

²⁹⁷ John Wesley, “Journal 5,” in W. Reginald Ward and Richard P. Heitzenrater, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 19, *Journal and Diaries II (1738-1743)*, by John Wesley, 23 August 1743, in p. 323.

²⁹⁸ Ibid.

²⁹⁹ Ibid., 23 August 1743, in p. 323-4.

³⁰⁰ Ibid., 23 August 1743, in p. 323.

irresistible at all times, since “no men living that have not many times ‘resisted the Holy Ghost’.”³⁰¹ He quotes Augustine’s words “[God] that made us *without ourselves* will not save us *without ourselves*”³⁰² to mean that God saves us with our consent – that is, God’s grace is resistible.³⁰³

Thus, according to Wesley, God’s grace is resistible in general but irresistible in particular occasions; it is irresistible in bringing faith and salvation to those who accept, it is irresistible in the conversions of some saints, and also it is irresistible to us in “some other times.” In other words, God’s grace is irresistible in its saving effects, but men may resist its effects. However there are occasions when they cannot resist.

Then, is prevenient grace irresistible? What Wesley means by “the grace which brings faith, and thereby salvation in the soul”³⁰⁴ is more towards convincing and justifying grace rather than prevenient grace. Wesley does not make any plain statements on whether prevenient grace is irresistible or not. However, as pointed out by Collins, “prevenient grace ... must be irresistibly given in order to restore humanity’s very ability to respond to the further grace of God. ...to deny that prevenient grace is irresistible is also to deny that Wesley held a doctrine of *total* depravity.”³⁰⁵ In other words, prevenient grace must irresistibly operate in every “natural man,” in order to give them “natural conscience,” so that they can respond to God’s further grace. Since there is no man in mere “natural state” and every man has “natural conscience,” (that is, prevenient grace operates in every one,)³⁰⁶ then no man can resist prevenient grace to operate in him as his “natural conscience.”

Since prevenient grace, which “is sufficient to *bring* us to Christ,”³⁰⁷ operates in every

³⁰¹ Wesley, “Sermon 63: The General Spread of the Gospel,” §12, in p. 490.

³⁰² Wesley, “Sermon 63: The General Spread of the Gospel,” §12, in p. 490, quoting Augustine, *Sermon 169: On Phil. 3:3-16*, xi (13).

³⁰³ See Wesley, “Sermon 63: The General Spread of the Gospel,” §12, in p. 490.

³⁰⁴ Wesley, “Journal 5,” 23 August 1743, in p. 323.

³⁰⁵ Kenneth J. Collins, *Wesley on Salvation: A Study in the Standard Sermons* (Grand Rapids: Francis Asbury Press, 1989), 24.

³⁰⁶ See Wesley, “Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Salvation,” III.4, in p. 207; Wesley, “The Principles of a Methodist,” §29, in p. 64, quoting Mr. Tucker.

³⁰⁷ *Ibid.*

one irresistibly, why then are not all men finally brought to Christ? This is because, firstly, although prevenient grace operates irresistibly as “natural conscience” in every man, every man has different measures of “natural conscience.”³⁰⁸ Prevenient grace is irresistible in the sense that it operates as “natural conscience” in everyone; it is resistible in the sense that although man cannot totally eliminate his natural conscience, he can resist his natural conscience to a lesser measure. In other words, although man cannot totally eliminate the operation of prevenient grace in him, he can resist it to a lesser measure. For example, a man will feel guilty when he steals for the first time. This guilt is a result of prevenient grace operating as his natural conscience. However, this man can choose to ignore his guilt and continue to steal. If he continues to steal, his guilt is reduced. Although finally he may not feel guilty at all when he steals, deep in his heart he knows that stealing is a sin. He can resist the operation of prevenient grace to a lesser measure, but he cannot totally eliminate it.

Secondly, besides “natural conscience,” prevenient grace also further operates through other means, including our faculties of “understanding,” “affections” and “liberty,” as well as God’s providence, and also means of grace. This further operation of prevenient grace can be resisted by man.

Thus, it is obvious that prevenient grace is both irresistible and resistible. Its irresistibility refers to its presence in the form of “natural conscience” in every man. Its resistibility refers to man’s ability to resist “natural conscience” to a lesser measure, and also his ability to resist further operation of prevenient grace. This is why although prevenient grace operates irresistibly in every man, not every man is brought to Christ.

Then, why are some brought to Christ but some not? This is because of their freedom to choose. While some choose to accept others reject their “natural conscience” and the further operation of prevenient grace. (It should be reminded that even man’s liberty to choose is also God’s prevenient grace, which is irresistible.) But why do some choose to accept while others

³⁰⁸ See Wesley, “Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Salvation,” III.4, in p. 207.

reject? Wesley does not answer this question directly. But in his explanation on why some believe while others do not,³⁰⁹ he gives us a principle that is appropriate to answer the question. The principle is that it is the mystery of God. Wesley writes, “God undoubtedly has reasons; but those reasons are generally hid[den] from the children of men.”³¹⁰ It is the mystery of God, beyond our understanding, why some choose to accept while others reject their “natural conscience” and the further operation of prevenient grace.

In conclusion, the ultimate effect of the operation of prevenient grace is to “*bring us to Christ.*” The operation of prevenient grace is both irresistible and resistible; this is why some men are finally brought to Christ but others are not, because although they cannot totally eliminate prevenient grace, they can choose to resist it to a lesser measure. As to why some choose to resist prevenient grace yet others do not is beyond our understanding; it is the mystery of God.

5.3.3 Conclusion

Prevenient grace is the operation of the Holy Spirit internally in the form of our “natural conscience” and through our faculties of “understanding,” “affections,” and “liberty”; and externally through God’s providence and means of grace. With the operation of prevenient grace, we are able to discern good and evil, be convicted of our sins, and able to choose good. Prevenient grace continues to operate in us in order to give us the “first repentance which is previous to faith in Christ”³¹¹ and finally “*bring us to Christ.*”

Prevenient grace is irresistible, for it operates as “natural conscience” in every man; yet it is also resistible, for man can resist repenting and coming to Christ. No one knows why some repent and come to Christ but some do not, for this is the mystery of God, which is beyond our understanding.

³⁰⁹ See Wesley, “Sermon 69: The Imperfection of Human Knowledge,” in Albert C. Outler, ed., *The Works of John Wesley*, vol. 2, *Sermons II: 34-70*, by John Wesley, III.5, in p. 584.

³¹⁰ Ibid.

³¹¹ Wesley, “Sermon 21: Sermon on the Mount, I,” I.4, p. 477.

5.4 Conclusion

Prevenient grace is God's power in Christ operating through the Holy Spirit before our justification in order to enable us to respond to God's further grace – “convincing,” “justifying” and “sanctifying” grace. Since we are all sinners, unable to respond to God's calling, prevenient grace is therefore necessary for our salvation. Prevenient grace is given freely and irresistibly to everyone in the form of “natural conscience,” but man can resist its further operation and effects. Prevenient grace is the pivot to balance the tension between the grace of God and the participation of men in Wesley's soteriology and doctrine of grace.

CHAPTER 6

A BRIEF COMPARISON OF AUGUSTINE AND WESLEY'S CONCEPTS OF PREVENIENT GRACE

In Chapters 3 and 5, we have respectively studied Augustine's and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace in the definition-nature-operation framework. Based on these two chapters, the author will go on to compare Augustine's and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace following the same framework, that is, the definition-nature-operation framework.

There are two reasons for using the same framework. First, by using the same framework the author can maintain consistency in the flow of thought for this thesis. Second, by using the same framework readers can easily make cross references. Since this comparison is based on studies done in Chapters 3 and 5, the author will only list out the statements or principles of their concepts of prevenient grace found in these two chapters and not discuss them in detail again.

Thus, by using the same framework, the readers can easily refer back to the respective parts for details. Hence, this chapter will compare their concepts following the definition-nature-operation framework.

6.1 Comparison on the Definitions of Prevenient Grace

Regarding the definition of prevenient grace, both Augustine and Wesley have one thing in common, that is, both of them do not define prevenient grace directly. Thus, the author of this thesis has to make an attempt to help consolidate definitions for them based on their works. As a result of this, these definitions may not be able to reflect totally and comprehensively their own understanding. However, the author believes that these definitions can give us some basic ideas on their meanings of prevenient grace.

For Augustine, prevenient grace is God's gift of assistance in Jesus Christ through the

Holy Spirit, which is prior to man's merits; this gift is totally on the ground of God's mercy, not depending on man's merits. For Wesley, prevenient grace is God's assistance given to us in the form of His power in Jesus Christ, operated by the Holy Spirit in everyone's heart in the form of his natural conscience.

From these definitions, it is obvious that there are five similarities. First, they agree that God is the origin of prevenient grace. Second, prevenient grace is only found in Jesus Christ. Third, the Holy Spirit is the only channel and agent of prevenient grace. Fourth, prevenient grace is the work of the triune God. Fifth, prevenient grace is God's gift of assistance.

In addition, there are two other similarities between their definitions. Augustine's definition, which is formed by the author, includes two elements. First, prevenient grace precedes man's merit. Second, prevenient grace is solely the mercy of God, which does not depend on men's merits. Although these are not included by the author in Wesley's definition, they are in fact found in Wesley's works.³¹² Thus, these are another two similarities between Augustine and Wesley's definitions.

However, there is one difference that distinguishes Wesley's definition from Augustine's. Wesley believes that prevenient grace is given to men in the form of natural conscience. Augustine will probably agree that the Holy Spirit may operate prevenient grace through men's natural conscience, but by no means will he agree that prevenient grace works in the form of men's natural conscience. This is because he may agree that *every* man has natural conscience, but he will totally reject that prevenient grace works in *every* man.

We shall not be contented with identifying the similarities and difference between their definitions only; we shall go beyond it by attempting to construct Augustine-Wesley's definition of prevenient grace. This can be done by putting all their similarities together. An Augustine-Wesley's definition, proposed by the author, is "prevenient grace is God's gift of assistance in the form of His power in Jesus Christ, operated by the Holy Spirit in man prior to

³¹² See 5.2.1, par. 4, 5.2.2, par. 1. and 5.3.2, par. 2. "Natural man" does not have any prior merits to earn "natural conscience," thus prevenient grace must be prior to men's merits.

his own merits and depends not on his merits, but solely on the ground of Christ's merits.

6.2 Comparison on the Natures of Prevenient Grace

In 3.2 and 5.2, from Augustine's and Wesley's works respectively the author had drawn out some principles on the natures of prevenient grace in the aspects of God the Giver and men the receivers. For Augustine, in the aspect of God the Giver, four principles had been drawn out.³¹³ First, prevenient grace is God's gratuitous and sovereign gift to men. Second, prevenient grace is God's gift in Jesus Christ conveyed by the Holy Spirit to men. Third, prevenience is the very nature of prevenient grace. Fourth, prevenient grace is not another but the same grace of God. Both prevenient grace and subsequent grace of God are the same grace of God that operates in different steps of the process of salvation.

Another two principles in the aspect of men the receivers had been drawn out as well.³¹⁴ First, prevenient grace is necessary for salvation. Second, prevenient grace is given freely to man; it requires no man's own merits.

For Wesley, in the aspect of God the Giver, three principles have been drawn out. First, prevenient, convincing, justifying and sanctifying grace are description for the same grace of God that operates in different stages in the process of salvation. Second, prevenient grace is God's power in Jesus Christ conveyed by the Holy Spirit. Third, prevenient grace is "free in all, and free for all."³¹⁵

In the aspect of men the receivers, three principles have been drawn out as well. First, prevenient grace is necessary for men. Second, since God's grace is "free in all,"³¹⁶ men cannot earn God's grace with own merits. Third, prevenient grace is "free for all,"³¹⁷ thus it is given to every man in the form of "natural conscience."³¹⁸

³¹³ See 3.2.1.

³¹⁴ See 3.2.2.

³¹⁵ Wesley, "Sermon 110: Free Grace," §2, in p. 544.

³¹⁶ Ibid.

³¹⁷ Ibid., §3, in p. 544.

³¹⁸ Wesley, "Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Own Salvation," III.4, in p. 307.

From these principles, it is obvious that there are four similarities in their teachings on the natures of prevenient grace. First, they agree that prevenient grace is not a separate grace of God, but is in fact the very same God's grace that operates before man's justification. Second, they agree that prevenient grace is God's gift of power in Jesus Christ conveyed by the Holy Spirit to men. Prevenient grace must be in Jesus Christ and through the Holy Spirit.³¹⁹ Third, they agree that prevenient grace is "free in all,"³²⁰ given freely to according to God's "undeserved favour,"³²¹ that it requires no man's merits and that man cannot earn it with his own merits. So it is God's gratuitous gift. Fourth, they agree that prevenient grace is necessary for man in his salvation.

However, there are also three differences in their teachings. First, Augustine teaches that prevenient grace is God's sovereign gift, which means it is given to those He has "predestined and called according to [His] divine purpose."³²² But for Wesley, prevenient grace is free for all, which means it is given to every man. This does not mean that Wesley denies the sovereignty of God, but what he denies is Augustine's interpretation of God's sovereignty. For Wesley, prevenient grace is given to every one, and the reason some believe and others do not is beyond our understanding – it is the mystery of God's counsel.³²³

Second, Augustine teaches that prevenient grace is necessary for man's salvation. But for Wesley, prevenient grace is not only necessary for our salvation, but also for our being and living.³²⁴ For Augustine, God's prevenient grace is given only to those God has predestined,³²⁵ thus it is needed for man's salvation. Augustine also teaches that all creatures have to depend on God's grace for their being, living and operation,³²⁶ but in Augustinian legacy following

³¹⁹ See 3.2.1 par. 2, 5.2.1 par.3, 5.3.1.2 par. 2.

³²⁰ Wesley, "Sermon 110: Free Grace," §2, in p. 544.

³²¹ Wesley, "Sermon 1: Salvation by Faith," III.3, in p. 126.

³²² Augustine, "On the Grace of Christ," chap. 13, in p. 400.

³²³ See 5.3.2, par. 9.

³²⁴ See 5.2.3, par. 2.

³²⁵ See 3.3.3.

³²⁶ *Augustine through the Ages: An Encyclopedia*, s.v. "Grace."

Calvin's theology this grace is called "'common' grace"³²⁷ rather than prevenient grace. For Wesley, this grace is also prevenient grace, because it operates before men's justification. Thus, to Augustine, prevenient grace only refers to God's grace that initiates man's salvation, but for Wesley, prevenient grace refers to God's grace that operates before men's justification.

Third, they use different terms to describe God's grace that operates during and after man's justification. For Augustine, he uses the term "subsequent grace"³²⁸ to distinguish it from God's grace that operates before justification. Augustine uses "subsequent grace"³²⁹ to denote God's grace that operates in all the stages of the process of salvation, from justification through sanctification to perfection. However, Wesley further divides what Augustine calls "subsequent grace" into three other terms, "convincing,"³³⁰ "justifying" and "sanctifying grace."³³¹ These three terms further describe the operation of God's grace in each stage of the process of salvation – repentance, justification, sanctification and perfection. In other words, Wesley makes a clearer distinction among the operations of God's grace at the different stages of the process of salvation.

To conclude, concerning the natures of prevenient grace, Wesley and Augustine have more similarities than differences. In other words, despite the three differences mentioned above, their teachings on the nature of prevenient grace are basically the same.

³²⁷ *New Dictionary of Theology*, 1989 ed., s.v. "Grace," by R. Kearsley. It should be noted that although John Calvin never used the term "common grace" in his works, but as pointed out by John Murray, this is a concept of Reformed tradition which should be credited to Calvin. (John Murray, *Common Grace* {article on-line} [Norwalk: Agape Chapel Ministries, n.d., accessed 10 October 2005]; available from http://www.sounddoctrine.net/LIBRARY/Modern%20Day%20Reform%20Teaching/John%20Murray/Common_Grace.htm; Internet; 1-2.) Although Louis Berkhof argued that Augustine "did not teach the doctrine of common grace" he did agree that Augustine "spoke of a grace which Adam enjoyed before the fall, and even admitted that man's existing as a living, sentient, and rational being might be termed grace." (Louis Berkhof, *Common Grace* {article on-line} [St. Louis: Covenant Theological Seminary, 2005, accessed 29 September 2005]; available from <http://www.mbrem.com/calvinism/commongrace.htm>; Internet; par. 2.) This grace, which is not saving grace, is what Reformed tradition calls "common grace," to differentiate it from particular grace (i.e., saving grace). Although there are different interpretations on "common grace," scholars come to agreement in three aspects: first, "common grace" prevents us from sinning; second, "common grace" does not save us; and third, common grace is given to every creature. See *New Dictionary of Theology*, "Grace," Murray, *Common Grace* and Louis Berkhof, *Common Grace*.

³²⁸ See Augustine, "A Treatise Against Two Letters of Pelagians," II.22, pp. 665-6.

³²⁹ Ibid.

³³⁰ Wesley, "Sermon 85: On Working Out Our Own Salvation," II.1, p. 204.

³³¹ Wesley, "Sermon 16: The Means of Grace," II.1, in p. 381.

6.3 Comparison on the Operation of Preventive Grace

Both Augustine and Wesley agree that the operation of preventive grace is the operation of the Holy Spirit. But do they agree with each other concerning the operations and effects of preventive grace?

6.3.1 Comparison on the Means of Operation

For Augustine, preventive grace operates externally on man through divine law, divine providence and baptism by the Church; and internally in man through his faculties of ability, will and doing. For Wesley, preventive grace operates externally on every man's heart through God's providence and Word, and also means of grace; and internally in the form of man's "natural conscience,"³³² which operates through his faculties of "understanding," "affections" and "liberty."³³³

Concerning the external means of operation, Augustine and Wesley have two similarities. First, they teach that God's law, or Word³³⁴ is the external means through which the Holy Spirit operates. They agree that it is the work of the Holy Spirit that reveals the spiritual meaning of the law of God to us, and thus convicts us of our sins.³³⁵

Second, they teach that the Holy Spirit also operates preventive grace through God's providence. However, to Wesley, God's providence refers to the direct intervention of the Holy Spirit in man's heart that awakens him from his spiritual indifference,³³⁶ but to Augustine it refers to God's control over environmental choice.³³⁷

Besides these two similarities, there exist two differences in Augustine's and Wesley's teachings on the external means of the operation of preventive grace. First, Augustine teaches that the Holy Spirit also operates preventive grace through baptism by the Church. According

³³² Wesley, "Sermon 43: The Scripture Way of Salvation," I.2, in p. 157.

³³³ Wesley, "Sermon 63: The General Spread of the Gospel," §11.

³³⁴ Wesley used the term "his Word" to refer to God's law. See V.3.1.2, par. 1.

³³⁵ See 3.3.1.1, pars. 1-2; 5.3.1.2, par. 1.

³³⁶ See 5.3.1.2, par. 1.

³³⁷ See 3.3.1.1, par. 4.

to Maddox, Wesley in his earlier years followed the “Western sacramental traditions” and accepted baptism, especially infant baptism, as a means of prevenient grace, but in his latter years, he replaced it with “natural conscience.”³³⁸ In other words, he dropped the teaching that baptism is a means of prevenient grace. This difference is due to his emphasis on the universality of prevenient grace,³³⁹ whereas Augustine teaches that prevenient grace is only for those elected.³⁴⁰

Second, Wesley teaches that the means of grace – “prayer,” “‘searching the Scriptures’,” and “partaking of the Lord’s Supper” – are “ordinary channels” designated by God to “convey to men preventing, justifying, or sanctifying grace.”³⁴¹ Among these three means of grace, Augustine may agree with two of them. First, since he teaches that God’s law, which is certainly God’s Word, is a means of grace, through which the Holy Spirit operates prevenient grace,³⁴² then he may agree that “‘searching the Scriptures’,” that is, studying the Bible is also a means of grace, through which the Holy Spirit operates prevenient grace. Second, Augustine may also agree that prayer is one of the means of grace that God conveys His prevenient grace.³⁴³ But Augustine will surely reject Wesley’s teachings that “partaking of the Lord’s Supper” is a means of grace conveying prevenient grace. This is because this teaching will lead to administering the Lord’s Supper to the unbelievers,³⁴⁴ which is certainly rejected by Augustine – for he asserts that only those who are baptized can partake the Lord’s Supper.³⁴⁵

Concerning the internal means of operation, both Augustine and Wesley teach that the Holy Spirit operates prevenient grace within men. But they have different teachings on how the Holy Spirit operates within men. First, Wesley teaches that the Holy Spirit operates prevenient

³³⁸ Maddox, *Responsible Grace*, 228-9.

³³⁹ See *ibid.*

³⁴⁰ See 3.3.3.

³⁴¹ Wesley, “Sermon 16: The Means of Grace,” II.1, III 1-12, in pp. 381, 384-90.

³⁴² See 3.3.1.1, pars. 1-3.

³⁴³ A further study is needed to prove this statement.

³⁴⁴ See 5.3.1.2, par. 5.

³⁴⁵ Augustine, “A Treatise on the Merits and Forgiveness of Sins, and on the Baptism of Infants,” I.26, p. 108-9.

grace in men's hearts as their "natural conscience," which is given by God to every man.³⁴⁶

This is certainly rejected by Augustine, for he believes that prevenient grace is given by God only to those He has chosen.³⁴⁷

Second, Wesley teaches that prevenient grace operates through men's faculties of "understanding," "affections" and "liberty,"³⁴⁸ whereas Augustine teaches that prevenient grace operates through men's faculties of ability, will and deed.³⁴⁹ In other words, for Wesley, prevenient grace operates in us to enlighten our reasoning faculty, to move our faculty of feeling and to enable our faculty of freedom;³⁵⁰ for Augustine, prevenient grace empowers our faculty of ability, moves our faculty of free will and affects our faculty of deed.³⁵¹ Actually they use different terms to describe the same thing – in essence their teachings are similar. What Augustine meant by the faculty of free will is actually similar to what Wesley meant by faculties of reasoning, feeling and freedom.³⁵² On the other hand, what Wesley meant by faculty of freedom actually includes what Augustine meant by faculties of ability, free will and deed.³⁵³

To conclude, on the one hand, both Augustine and Wesley teaches that the Holy Spirit operates prevenient grace externally through God's providence and Word, and also internally within men. But it should be reminded that they have different opinions on how God's providence acts upon men. On the other hand, they disagree with each other in two points. First, Wesley rejects Augustine's teaching that baptism is the external means of the operation of prevenient grace. Neither Augustine will agree with Wesley in his teaching that "partaking the Lord's Supper" is a means of prevenient grace. Second, Augustine will surely reject Wesley's teaching that prevenient grace operates as "natural conscience" in men.

³⁴⁶ Wesley, "Sermon 105: On Conscience," I.5, in p. 482. See V.3.1.1, par. 1.

³⁴⁷ See 3.3.3, par. 1.

³⁴⁸ Wesley, "Sermon 63: The General Spread of the Gospel," §11. See V.3.1.1, par. 2.

³⁴⁹ See 3.3.1.2.

³⁵⁰ See 5.3.1.1, par. 2.

³⁵¹ See 3.3.1.2.

³⁵² See 3.3.1.2, and 5.3.1.2, par. 2.

³⁵³ See 3.3.1.2, and 5.3.1.2, par. 2.

6.3.2 Comparison on the Effects of the Operation

In terms of the effects of the operation of prevenient grace, as identified by the author in 3.3.2, Augustine teaches that prevenient grace initiates and completes the process of our salvation. According to him, the operation of prevenient grace is irresistible.³⁵⁴ As for Wesley, the ultimate effect of the operation of prevenient grace is to “*bring us to Christ.*”³⁵⁵ According to Wesley, the operation of prevenient grace is both resistible and irresistible.³⁵⁶

From their teachings on the effects of the operation of prevenient grace, it is obvious that both of them agree that prevenient grace initiates the process of our salvation,³⁵⁷ or is “sufficient to *bring us to Christ*” for justification.³⁵⁸ In other words, both of them agree that prevenient grace leads us to justification, but for Wesley it is not enough to justify us.

Besides initiating the process of our salvation, Augustine believes that prevenient grace also completes the process of our salvation. However, to Wesley the completion of our salvation is the work of justifying and sanctifying grace. Such a difference is due to their different emphases on prevenient grace. Prevenient grace has a twofold meaning. First, it precedes men’s merits. Second, it precedes justification. Both Augustine and Wesley have this twofold meaning in their teachings regarding prevenient grace. However, they still have different emphases. For Augustine, his emphasis is on the first meaning of prevenient grace, that is, it precedes our merits before the beginning and throughout the course and to the completion of our salvation. But for Wesley, his emphasis is on the second meaning of prevenient grace, that is, it precedes our justification. In other words, Wesley’s concern is on the practical aspect of prevenient grace. He makes a clearer distinction between prevenient grace and God’s grace that operates after prevenient grace.

In terms of the effects of the operation of prevenient grace, it should be noted that

³⁵⁴ See 3.3.2, par. 7.

³⁵⁵ Wesley, “The Principles of a Methodist,” §29, in p. 64, quoting Mr. Tucker. See 5.3.2, pars. 2 and 10.

³⁵⁶ See 5.3.2, pars. 5-10.

³⁵⁷ See 3.3.2.

³⁵⁸ Wesley, “The Principles of a Methodist,” §29, in p.64, quoting Mr. Tucker. See 5.3.2, par. 2.

Wesley also teaches that prevenient grace causes our existence and sustains our being and living.³⁵⁹ Augustine also agrees that God’s grace is needed for the being, living and operation of all creatures,³⁶⁰ but as interpreted by Reformed tradition, this grace is called “‘common’ grace”³⁶¹ rather than prevenient grace. This is because in Augustine’s teachings, God’s grace – both prevenient and subsequent grace – is irresistible.³⁶² Following this logic, if it is prevenient grace that causes the existence and sustains the being and living of all men, then every man, without any exception, must be saved. But to him this is not true in reality. Thus it should not be prevenient grace that causes the existence and sustains the being and living of all men. In addition, there are unbelievers who are virtuous even though they do not believe in Jesus Christ, not even to their last breath. If it is prevenient grace that works in them, which according to Augustine is irresistible, then they must believe. Thus, it should not be the prevenient grace that works in the unbelievers. Therefore, a new term – “‘common’ grace”³⁶³ – is applied to differentiate God’s grace (that works in every man but not necessary to bring him to salvation) from prevenient grace.

However, the assertion of “‘common’ grace”³⁶⁴ is a logical flaw in Reformed theology, and if Reformed theology really reflects Augustine’s teachings, then common grace is also a logical flaw in Augustine’s theology. In Augustine’s doctrine of grace, which is an adaptation of “Neoplatonic theory of emanation,”³⁶⁵ God’s grace must be irresistible.³⁶⁶ Common grace is God’s grace. Thus, common grace must also be irresistible. Since common grace is given to all men,³⁶⁷ and it is irresistible, then it must cause every man to have good virtue. But in reality not all men have good virtue. Thus, it must be either common grace being not irresistible or common grace not given to every man. Both conclusions are not in compliance with the two

³⁵⁹ See 5.2.2, par. 2.

³⁶⁰ *Augustine through the Ages: An Encyclopedia*, s.v. “Grace.”

³⁶¹ *New Dictionary of Theology*, 1989 ed., s.v. “Grace,” by R. Kearsley.

³⁶² See 3.3.2, pars. 5-8.

³⁶³ *New Dictionary of Theology*, 1989 ed., s.v. “Grace,” by R. Kearsley.

³⁶⁴ *Ibid.*

³⁶⁵ *Augustine through the Ages: An Encyclopedia*, s.v. “Grace.”

³⁶⁶ See 3.3.2, par. 7.

³⁶⁷ Berkhof, *Common Grace*, B.1.

premises – common grace is irresistible and is given to every man. This is the logical flaw in Augustine’s doctrine of grace, if Reformed interpretation on his doctrine of grace is right.

By introducing prevenient grace as being both irresistible and resistible,³⁶⁸ Wesley had solved this logical flaw. Wesley’s concept of prevenient grace includes Calvin’s (or Augustine’s) common grace. But how can prevenient grace be both irresistible and resistible? Or is it logically valid that prevenient grace is both irresistible and resistible? It is a matter of time. Prevenient grace is first given to every one irresistibly, but every man can resist its effects to a lesser degree at other times. Thus, it is logically valid that prevenient grace is both irresistible and resistible.

By introducing prevenient grace as being both irresistible at one time and resistible at other times, Wesley can answer why among the unbelievers some have good virtue but others do not. The reason why some accept and others reject the operation of prevenient grace, according to Wesley, is beyond our understanding – it is the mystery of God’s counsel. This is Wesley’s interpretation of God’s sovereignty – God’s counsel is beyond our understanding. Thus, Wesley’s concept on the irresistibility and resistibility of prevenient grace preserves the integrity of God’s grace and sovereignty.³⁶⁹

To conclude, both Augustine and Wesley agree that prevenient grace leads us to salvation, but for Wesley it is not enough to justify us. But for Augustine, prevenient grace also completes the process of salvation – it is God’s grace, both prevenient and subsequent at the same time, leads us to justification, justifies us, sanctifies us and makes us perfect. Besides, for Augustine prevenient grace is irresistible, but for Wesley it is both irresistible and resistible.

6.3.3 Comparison on the Scope of the Operation

Regarding the scope of the operation of prevenient grace, Augustine and Wesley have

³⁶⁸ See 5.3.2, pars. 5-10.

³⁶⁹ It is interesting that in defending his position that God’s grace is not irresistible at all times, Wesley quotes Augustine’s works. Thus, in Wesley interpretation, at least concerning Augustine’s works he cited, Augustine also teaches that God’s grace is not irresistible at all times. See 5.3.2, par. 3.

different teachings. For Augustine, prevenient grace is only given to the elects,³⁷⁰ but for Wesley, it is given to every one.³⁷¹ This is due to their different teachings on the irresistibility of prevenient grace. For Augustine, prevenient grace is irresistible, that is, it must effect salvation. If it is given to every man, then all men should be saved. But not all men are saved, thus prevenient grace is only given to those God had chosen. On the other hand, for Wesley, prevenient grace is both irresistible and resistible. Thus, it can be given to every man irresistibly, and at the same time not all men are saved.

6.3.4 Conclusion

Concerning the means of operation, both Augustine and Wesley agrees that the Holy Spirit operates prevenient grace externally through God's providence and Word, and internally within men. But they have different opinions on how the Holy Spirit operates through these means. Concerning the effects of operation, both of them agree that prevenient grace leads us to justification, but for Wesley it is not sufficient to justify us. For Augustine, the operation of prevenient grace is irresistible at all times, that is, it must be effectual; but for Wesley, it is both irresistible and resistible. Concerning the scope of operation, they disagree with each other. For Augustine, prevenient grace is only given to the elect, but for Wesley, it is given to every one.

6.4 Conclusion

Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace are basically the same, for the similarities outnumber differences. There are 16 similarities and 11 differences. Almost all the similarities may be summarized in one statement – God's gift of power in Jesus Christ operated by the Holy Spirit externally through God's Word, providence and man's prayer, as well as internally within man through his faculties of reasoning, feeling, free will, ability and deed; this grace precedes men's merits, operates before our justification, is necessary for men's salvation,

³⁷⁰ See 3.3.3.

³⁷¹ See 3.3.2.

and is “free in all.”³⁷² Among the 11 differences, the major difference is that for Augustine, prevenient grace is irresistible for the elect, but for Wesley, prevenient grace is both irresistible and resistible for all. In other words, for Wesley, prevenient grace is free for all, but for Augustine, it is not free for all. The other minor differences are their teachings on the means of prevenient grace and their different emphases on prevenient grace. To sum up, according to Wesley, prevenient grace is God’s gift that is free in all and free for all, but according to Augustine, prevenient grace is God’s gift that is free in all, but not free for all.

³⁷² Wesley, “Sermon 110: Free Grace,” §2, in p. 544.

CONCLUSION

In this chapter, the author will make a summary on previous chapters, identify the essential differences and similarities between Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace, identify relationships between Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace, and suggest some implications from this study.

Summary on Previous Chapters

In chapter 1, it is shown that Wesley agreed with and used Augustine in some theological concepts but criticised him in other topics. Thus, Wesley probably had read Augustine's works widely, and a relationship might exist between Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace.

In chapter 2, we reviewed briefly Warfield and Burns' studies on Augustine's doctrine of grace, and from their frameworks the author developed a definition-nature-operation framework to study briefly Augustine's concept of prevenient grace in chapter 3.

In chapter 4, we examined briefly Outler, Collins and Maddox's works on Wesley's soteriology and doctrine of grace. In this chapter, it is also proven that the definition-nature-operation framework is also suitable to analyse briefly Wesley's concept of prevenient grace in chapter 5.

Based on the studies in chapter 3 and 5, the author in Chapter 6 made a comparison between Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace, following the same definition-nature-operation framework. It is good for us to review again this chapter in order to have a clearer picture regarding the similarities and differences between Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace. The author will outline the results of this comparison in the following table:

Table 1 List of Similarities and differences between Augustine and Wesley's Concept of Prevenient Grace

Similarities	Differences
I Definitions of Prevenient Grace	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Prevenient grace is the gift of God. 2) Prevenient grace is only found in Jesus Christ. 3) Prevenient grace is operated by the Holy Spirit only; the Holy Spirit is the only channel and agent of prevenient grace. 4) Prevenient grace is the work of the triune God. 5) Prevenient grace is God's assistance to men. 6) Prevenient grace precedes men's merits. 7) Prevenient grace is solely the mercy of God, does not depend on men's merits. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Wesley teaches that prevenient grace is given to men in the form of natural conscience. This is totally rejected by Augustine.
II Natures of Prevenient Grace	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Prevenient grace is not a separate grace of God, but is the very same grace of God that operates before men's justification. 2) Prevenient grace is God's gift of power in Jesus Christ conveyed by the Holy Spirit to men. 3) Prevenient grace is "free in all." 4) Prevenient grace is necessary for man in his salvation. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) For Augustine, prevenient grace is God's sovereign gift. For Wesley, it is a mystery of God's counsel as to why in the end some repent and some do not. 2) For Wesley, prevenient grace is needed also for our being and living. But according to Calvin's interpretation of Augustine's theology, it is common grace that causes our being and sustains our living. 3) Augustine calls grace after prevenient grace as subsequent grace, whereas Wesley further divides it into "convincing," "justifying" and "sanctifying grace."
III Operation of Prevenient Grace	
<i>III.1 Means of Operation</i>	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Prevenient grace operates through God's providence. 2) Prevenient grace operates through God's Word. 3) Prevenient grace operates through prayer. 4) Prevenient grace is operated by the Holy Spirit within man through his faculties of reasoning, feeling, free will, ability and deed. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) To Augustine, God's providence refers to God's control over environmental choice. But to Wesley, it refers to the direct operation of the Holy Spirit in men's hearts. 2) Augustine teaches that baptism is a means for the operation of prevenient grace; this teaching is dropped by Wesley finally. 3) Wesley teaches that the Holy Communion is a means of prevenient grace; but this teaching is totally rejected by Augustine. 4) Wesley teaches that the Holy Spirit operates prevenient grace within man in the form of his natural conscience. This teaching is rejected by Augustine.

<i>III.2 Effects of Operation</i>	
1) Prevenient grace leads us to justification.	1) For Augustine, prevenient grace is a nature of God's grace that runs through the course of salvation. But for Wesley, prevenient grace refers specifically to God's grace before justification. 2) For Augustine, the operation of prevenient grace is irresistible at all times. But for Wesley, it is both irresistible and resistible.
<i>III.3 Scope of Operation</i>	
	1) For Augustine, prevenient grace is given to the elects only, but for Wesley, prevenient grace is given to all people.

Augustine's and Wesley's Concepts of Prevenient Grace: Essential Difference

From the 11 differences identified in chapter 5, can we identify the essential differences between Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace? In the conclusion of chapter V, the author identified the major difference which is their disagreement in the irresistibility and the scope of the operation. For Augustine, prevenient grace is irresistible and not free for everyone, but for Wesley it is both resistible and irresistible, and it is free for everyone.

What are the essential differences of their teachings that result in these 11 differences? It is the dynamics that run through their theologies. As identified by Burns, the underlying philosophical framework of Augustine's doctrine of grace is the "Neoplatonic theory of emanation."³⁷³ Thus, derived from this philosophical framework, the dynamic force of Augustine's doctrine of grace is the transcendence and sovereignty of God. (In Warfield term, Augustine's doctrine of grace is "theocentric."³⁷⁴) Following this dynamic, in Augustine's doctrine of grace, God's grace (including prevenient grace) must be irresistible, and thus it is given only to those God has elected according to His sovereignty.

However, as concluded by Outler, Collins and Maddox,³⁷⁵ the dynamic in Wesley's

³⁷³ *Augustine through the Ages: An Encyclopedia*, 1999 ed., s. v. "Grace," by J. Patout Burns.

³⁷⁴ Warfield, "Introductory Essay on Augustin and the Pelagian Controversy," 70.

³⁷⁵ See 4.4, par. 3.

doctrine of grace is the tension between grace of God and participation of men. This dynamic allows two opposite teachings – God’s sovereignty and men’s responsibility – to exist together in Wesley’s doctrine of grace. Following this dynamic, God’s prevenient grace can be both irresistible at one time, but resistible at other times, and is given to every man, yet not every man will finally come to Christ. God is sovereign in giving every man His prevenient grace irresistibly, and at the same time allowing men to accept or resist the subsequent operation and effects of His prevenient grace.

To conclude, Augustine’s emphasis is on God’s sovereignty, and Wesley’s concern is on both God’s sovereignty and men’s responsibility in salvation. This is the divisive point between Augustine’s and Wesley’s concepts of prevenient grace.

Augustine’s and Wesley’s Concepts of Prevenient Grace: Essential Similarity

Besides the essential differences, are there any essential similarities between Augustine’s and Wesley’s concepts of prevenient grace? Warfield identified Augustine’s doctrine of grace “revolved around his conception of God as the immanent and vital spirit in whom all things live and move and have their beings.”³⁷⁶ In other words, the other dynamic force in Augustine’s doctrine of grace is the immanence of God in the person of the Holy Spirit. This is true for both Augustine and Wesley’s concepts of prevenient grace, for they teach that prevenient grace is operated by the Holy Spirit in us. Thus, the immanence of God the Holy Spirit is the essential similarity between their concepts of prevenient grace.

Relationships between Augustine and Wesley’s Concepts of Prevenient Grace

From the 11 differences and 16 similarities, can we identify any relationships between Augustine and Wesley in the aspect of their concepts of prevenient grace? The 16 similarities may suggest that Wesley might have been influenced directly or indirectly by Augustine in his

³⁷⁶ Warfield, “Introductory Essay on Augustin and the Pelagian Controversy,” 70.

concept of prevenient grace. Wesley might have been influenced directly by Augustine through his reading of Augustine's works. In supporting the resistibility of God's grace, Wesley even quoted Augustine's works.³⁷⁷ This is a strong point to prove that Wesley had read and used Augustine's writings in constructing his doctrine of grace. Further, Wesley might also have been influenced indirectly by Augustine by following Augustinian legacy, which is through his reading on and use of the works of those who followed Augustine's teachings.

However, these 16 similarities may also suggest that Wesley had been influenced by the same influence that influenced Augustine. In other words, in constructing his doctrine of grace, Wesley might have read and used the same sources that Augustine had read and used, such as Blackmore's "An Ode to the Divine Being and Saint Theresa,"³⁷⁸ as well as the Bible.

On the other hand, the 11 differences may suggest that besides reading and using Augustine's works or the same sources that Augustine used, Wesley also read and used other sources in constructing his doctrine of grace. The differences may also suggest that in constructing his doctrine of grace, Wesley had read Augustine's works, but he did not agree with him at all points and had made some corrections. A good example is his teaching that prevenient grace is both irresistible at one time and resistible at other times. This teaching might have been developed from other sources, and used by Wesley to correct the logical fallacy in Augustine's doctrine of grace.

The 11 differences may also suggest that Wesley might have read Augustine's works and further developed Augustine's doctrine of grace into a more systematic and detailed teaching. Two examples are, first, Wesley confined prevenient grace to God's grace before justification. In other words, Wesley had made prevenient grace more specific to the operation of God's grace in certain moments, whereas Augustine had treated prevenient grace as a nature of God's grace that ran through the whole course of salvation. Second, Wesley had further

³⁷⁷ See 5.3.2, par. 3. Wesley might have misunderstood Augustine's writings, for it had been argued in III.3.1.2 that to Augustine, God's grace is resistible.

³⁷⁸ See 1.4, par. 3

divided Augustine's subsequent grace into convincing, justifying and sanctifying grace. Again, this shows that Wesley's concern is on the exact operation of God's grace at different stages of salvation. Wesley had made his teachings on prevenient grace more detailed and systematic than Augustine's.

In conclusion, although there is only one direct quotation from Augustine's works by Wesley concerning the doctrine of grace,³⁷⁹ there are many similarities between their concepts of prevenient grace. This may be due to the direct and indirect influence of Augustine on Wesley, or some of the sources Wesley used in constructing his doctrine of grace which were the same as the sources Augustine used, such as Blackmore's "An Ode to the Divine Being" and Saint Theresa,³⁸⁰ as well as the Bible.

The differences actually also suggested another kind of relationship between Augustine and Wesley. Wesley might have read Augustine's works, and together with other sources he had reflected on Augustine's doctrine of grace. He further corrected on the topics that he disagreed with Augustine, or further developed on Augustine's works on some topics. Thus, from Wesley's direct quotation, the similarities and differences between Augustine and Wesley, we may infer that both positive and negative relationships exist between their concepts of prevenient grace.

However, the fairest conclusion that we can make from the similarities and differences between Augustine and Wesley's concepts of grace, is that, Wesley concurs with Augustine on many topics but disagrees with him only on some others.

Implications

What are the implications from this study? First, prevenient grace is not a new idea invented by Wesley. The concept of prevenient grace can be found in the writings of one of the

³⁷⁹ See 5.3.2, par. 3.

³⁸⁰ See 1.4, par. 3

most prominent and influential Church Fathers, that is, Augustine.

Second, since prevenient grace is not a new idea, as it can also be found in Augustine's writings, it is unfair to condemn Wesley's soteriology as semi-Pelagianism. The point that distinguishes Wesley's soteriology from Pelagianism is Wesley's teachings on prevenient grace. Since prevenient grace is not a new idea invented by Wesley, and since there are many similarities between Wesley and Augustine's concepts of prevenient grace, then instead of labelling Wesley's soteriology semi-Pelagian, it is perhaps justifiable to call it "semi-Augustinian."³⁸¹

Third, Augustine and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace complement each other. Augustine and Wesley have different emphases in their teachings of prevenient grace, which may be overlooked by the other party. In other words, we can have a more comprehensive understanding on prevenient grace by studying both their concepts of prevenient grace. We may even take a further step. We may reorganise all the 16 similarities, with consideration of the 11 differences, to construct an Augustine-Wesley's concept of prevenient grace. In the conclusion of the previous chapter, the author has condensed 16 similarities into one statement – God's gift of power in Jesus Christ operated by the Holy Spirit externally through God's Word, providence and man's prayer, as well as internally within man through his faculties of reasoning, feeling, free will, ability and deed; this grace precedes men's merits, operates before our justification, is necessary for men's salvation, and is "free in all."³⁸² This is a simplified version of the Augustine-Wesley's concept of prevenient grace.

Fourth, with this understanding of the Augustine-Wesley's concept of prevenient grace, we will appreciate much of God's grace. It is totally because of God's grace that we are saved. We have no merits in our salvation. Even the first good thought we have is the result of the operation of prevenient grace. Thus, what we can do is only to give thanks to our God, the

³⁸¹ By "semi-Augustinian" the author means Wesley's concept of prevenient grace is basically the same with Augustine's concept of prevenient grace. However, this term employed by the author as a refutation against Calvinist's condemnation that Wesley's concept of prevenient grace is semi-Pelagian.

³⁸² Wesley, "Sermon 110: Free Grace," §2, in p. 544.

source of grace.

Fifth, with a more comprehensive understanding on prevenient grace, we can have a more comprehensive understanding on our role in evangelism. Prevenient grace operates externally through God's providence, Word and man's prayer, and externally within man's faculties of reasoning, feeling, free will, ability and deed. Among these means of grace, we can contribute nothing to the first means – God's providence, for it is exclusively God's works. But we can co-operate with God's grace through other means. We can pray for people, preach God's Word (including God's law) in a rational and passionate way that appeals to their faculties of reasoning and feeling, and encourage them to use their free will (which is already restored by prevenient grace) to choose (faculties of ability and deed) to believe Jesus Christ; these are our roles in evangelism. We do not cause people to be saved or to believe; it is prevenient grace that first leads them to Christ, then God's grace further causes them to believe in Christ and to be saved. We are only the instruments of God's prevenient grace, which is used by God to co-operate with prevenient grace.

Sixth, this study has suggested some possible relationships between Augustine and Wesley's concept of prevenient grace. However, these suggestions are inferred from their similarities and differences. Thus, further studies can be carried out to examine these relationships.

Seventh, besides relationships between Augustine and Wesley in the aspect of prevenient grace, relationships in other theological concepts may also exist between them. Thus, this study opens up a new era of study, that is, to study the relationships between Augustine and Wesley in various other theological concepts.

Finally, when more relationships between Augustine and Wesley are discovered, we may construct an Augustinian-Wesleyan legacy, which will contribute a lot to the growth of our church and ourselves.

Conclusion

This thesis has accomplished its goal of making an explorative comparison between Augustine's and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace. It provides us with a new perspective in understanding Augustine's and Wesley's concepts of prevenient grace, that is, they complement each other. It provides us with the significance of Augustine-Wesley concept of prevenient grace in present day, which is in our spiritual life, evangelism and also further study on the inferred relationships between them. It opens to us a new era of study, and a challenge to construct an Augustinian-Wesleyan legacy.

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